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Exploring Visions of a Just and Sustainable City: A Q-Survey of Brussels' Stakeholders

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Submission date	May 2024
Dissemination level	Public
Keywords	Just urban transitions; Just sustainabilities; Urban studies; Futures studies; Visions; Q methodology

Summary

In recent years, the concept of ‘just transition’ has evolved from a narrow *social* project, aimed at protecting workers in industries affected by environmental regulations, to a comprehensive *social-ecological* project aimed at addressing social inequalities and environmental degradation in an integrated way. This integrated pursuit of social justice and environmental sustainability objectives is particularly relevant for the urban context, where social and ecological issues concentrate and intertwine. Despite the growing prominence of just transition imperatives in urban agendas, questions of what a just *and* sustainable city could and should look like remain under-investigated.

Against that background, the main objective of the present research is to explore urban visions that explicitly combine social justice and environmental sustainability objectives. More specifically, this research aims at 1) outlining contrasting visions of a just and sustainable city in the Brussels Capital Region, 2) identifying the actors who support these visions, and 3) highlighting the areas of consensus and debate on the issue. With that aim in mind, we conducted a survey of Brussels’ stakeholders based on a Q-methodology, i.e., a statistically supported survey method for understanding the plurality of perspectives on a topic within a group. This survey was carried out between December 2023 and January 2024, and 32 representatives of administrations and other public institutions, NGOs and associations, business federations, trade unions and citizen movements took part.

The statistical analysis of survey data and the interpretation of its results led to the definition of three contrasted urban visions bridging social justice and environmental sustainability objectives: The ‘**Smart City**’, the ‘**Foundational City**’ and the ‘**Exnovation City**’. The main distinguishing characteristics of these visions of the just and sustainable city reflecting the different perspectives of Brussels’ stakeholders are summarised in the figure below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Overview of the three visions of a just and sustainable city in Brussels-Capital-Region¹

¹ The pictures were generated with artificial intelligence.

The vision of the 'Foundational City' is the one with the highest number of survey respondents endorsing it, while the 'Smart City' vision is the one with the fewest. Regarding the type of stakeholder supporting the different visions identified, we find members of administrations and other public organisations subscribing to each of the three visions. On their part, the representatives of the NGOs and associations consulted promote either the 'Foundational City' or the 'Exnovation City' visions. As for the business' federations, the two respondents representing eco-companies embrace the 'Foundational City' vision, while the other two representing incumbent companies adhere to the 'Smart City' vision. Finally, all the three trade unionists and the only member of a citizen's movement who took part in the survey support the vision of the 'Foundational City'.

Each of the three visions of the just and sustainable city can be associated with a specific conception of 'just sustainability'. In the 'Smart City', it equates inclusive and sustainable economic development, i.e., an economic growth decoupled from its environmental degradation and delivering social justice. The 'Foundational City' abandons the imperatives of economic growth and understands 'just sustainability' as a juxtaposition of intragenerational justice – i.e., justice between different humans of the present generation – and intergenerational justice – i.e., justice between humans of different generations –. The 'Exnovation City' goes beyond an anthropocentric conception of justice and interprets 'just sustainability' as an integration of ecological justice – i.e., justice for nature – with environmental justice – i.e., justice between different humans in relation to their natural environment –.

The three visions of the just and sustainable city can further be distinguished by the relative priority they give to the objectives of economic growth, social justice and environmental sustainability. Indeed, if a trade-off arises between some of these objectives, the 'Smart City' will tend to prioritise economic growth seen as a source of trickle-down prosperity, the 'Foundational City' will tend to put the fulfilment of fundamental human needs and social equity first, and the 'Exnovation City' will tend to give priority to the preservation and restoration of nature deemed necessary for sustaining a good and fulfilling life for all. The priority differential between the three visions of the just and sustainable city reflects the challenges of simultaneously fostering economic growth, social justice and environmental sustainability, and the inherent tensions and conflicts between these three objectives of sustainable development.

Beyond this priority differential, the cross-analysis of the three visions offers additional insights on the terms of the debate among Brussels' stakeholders on what a just and sustainable city should look like. Among the most controversial topics, we find the future of the capitalist system and the neo-liberal approach to the city, the place of exnovation in the transition to a just and sustainable city, the role of technology – and notably digital technology – in the deployment of ecological modes of production and consumption, the establishment of a ceiling on income and assets, the (de-)densification of the city, and the provision of universal access to decent and affordable housing in Brussels.

Besides these divergences, the analysis also highlights some areas of consensus. In this respect, the most striking point of convergence between the three visions of a just and sustainable city lies in the high priority given to the health of the city's residents. This paves the way for the construction of a vision of a just and sustainable city centred on health shared by all Brussels' stakeholders, which could lead to the adoption of 'full health' as a compass to guide the just transition in Brussels-Capital Region.

By identifying and exploring three original visions of Brussels bridging social justice and environmental sustainability objectives, this research contributes to understanding the contours of the future(s) towards which just urban transitions could orient, alongside the main disagreements and consensus on this issue. It thus provides fruitful ground for open debate and further research on just transitions in Brussels-Capital Region and other metropolitan areas.

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1. Introduction

Following its inclusion as a guiding principle in the Paris Agreement in 2015, the concept of ‘just transition’ has gained ground in political agendas and discourses at all levels, from global to local (Jones, 2022; Ciplet, 2022; Galgóczi 2022; Abram et al., 2022; Stevis and Felli, 2020). More and more cities have thus committed to ensuring a just transition (Steele and Dodson, 2022; Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019), including the Brussels-Capital Region (BCR). Since 2021, Brussels' government has indeed made the just transition a guiding principle of its climate policy and enshrined it in the Brussels Code on Air, Climate and Energy Management². This legal text, which forms the basis of the main environmental strategies and plans of the BCR, provides for the regional climate policy to be guided by “the principle of social justice and just transition, which implies that the prevention and reduction of social inequalities and situations of precariousness are an integral part of the development and implementation of climate policies”.

This definition of just transition adopted by the Brussels' governments can be associated with a comprehensive acceptance of just transition as a *social-ecological* project aimed at addressing in an integrated way social inequalities and environmental degradation (Fransolet et Vanhille, 2023; Krause et al., 2022; Ciplet, 2022; Cha and Pastor, 2022; Burke 2022; Bauler et al., 2021; Clarke and Lipsig-Mummé, 2020). This comprehensive approach to just transition, which goes beyond the original acceptance of protecting workers from environmental policies (Wilgosh et al, 2022; Abram et al., 2022), has become increasingly widespread in recent years (Luke, 2023; Burke 2022; Abram et al., 2022; Bauler et al., 2021). It is, for instance, also found in the *Build Back Better* framework adopted in the UK and US, which had the objective of addressing the socio-economic impacts of the COVID-19 crisis by simultaneously reducing environmental degradation and long-standing inequalities (Lacey-Barnacle et al., 2023), but also in the US Green New Deal, which aims to decarbonize the economy while improving justice by promoting, *inter alia*, adequate housing, quality food and health care for all (Cha and Pastor, 2022).

A just transition project aimed at pursuing in an integrated way social justice and environmental sustainability objectives is particularly relevant for the urban context, where social and ecological issues concentrate and intertwine. Cities are, indeed, disproportionately responsible for many contemporary environmental problems, including climate change, air and water pollution, biodiversity loss, resource depletion and waste production (Steele and Dodson, 2022; Jänicke, 2015). They notably contribute to more than 70% of global CO₂ emissions, a large part of which are associated with their fossil fuel-intensive industrial and transportation systems (Dasgupta et al., 2022). In turn, environmental problems disproportionately affect vulnerable urban residents (De Muynck and Ragot, 2022; Shen et al., 2020), thus contributing to widening existing inequalities in cities (Steele and Dodson, 2022; Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019; Béné et al., 2017). In fact, cities have historically concentrated many forms of injustices and inequalities (Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019). It is also at this scale that “questions of justice are felt concretely as part of everyday life” (Connolly and Steil 2009, p. 6). And over time, we have not seen a reduction in inequalities, but rather an increase from the 1970s following the advent of the “Neoliberal City” (Dlabac et al. 2022; Granberg and Glover, 2021; Connolly and Steil 2009; Novy and Mayer 2009), and even more in recent years due to the increasingly perceptible impacts of climate change, but also as a result of the socio-economic consequences of the COVID-19 crisis (Steele and Dodson, 2022) and the explosion in energy prices associated with the war in Ukraine (Galgóczi, 2022).

Despite the growing prominence of just transition imperatives in urban agendas, questions of what a just and sustainable city could and should look like remain underexplored. Based on a review of the literature, Hughes and Hoffmann (2019) show, on the one hand, that research on just transitions in

² <https://environnement.brussels/pro/nos-actions/plans-et-politiques-regionales/le-code-bruxellois-de-lair-du-climat-et-de-la-maitrise-de-lenergie-cobrace>

urban contexts is only at its infancy and, on the other hand, that most of this research is retrospective and evaluative, while future-oriented analyses are lacking (Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019). This gap is particularly evident in research on just transition carried out in the Brussels-Capital Region, among which we find investigations on the existing inequalities in exposure and vulnerability to climate risks (De Muynck and Ragot, 2022; De Muynck et al., 2022) or critical analysis of the implementation of the low-emission zone with regard to social-ecological justice criteria (Callorda Fossati et al., forthcoming). However, there is a lack of research, in the BCR and beyond, exploring just sustainable urban futures and the transition pathways needed to bring them about. Yet, to support cities in the elaboration and implementation of just transition, it is essential to move “beyond diagnosing injustices and building a positive case for, and pathways to, just and equitable [environmentally sustainable] cities” (Hughes and Hoffmann 2019, p. 2). This involves notably the following questions: What could a just *and* sustainable city look like? What policies could be developed and implemented to ensure just urban transitions? By which actors? How can we monitor and evaluate these transition processes?

Against that background, the present research intends to contribute to understanding the contours of the just *and* sustainable futures toward which just urban transitions could orient. This exploration of just sustainabilities in an urban context does not start from scratch. There is, indeed, a broad array of literature conceptualising visions of the ‘just city’ and the ‘sustainable city’. On the one hand, since the 1990s, many authors have imagined the contours of utopian cities promoting in different ways distributive, procedural and recognitional justice principles. Some of the most influential conceptualizations of the just city have been notably proposed by Susan Fainstein (2010) in ‘The Just city’, by Leonie Sandercock (1998) in ‘Cosmopolis’ or again by John Forester (1988) in ‘Planning in the face of Power’. On the other hand, the literature on environmental sustainability is full of conceptualizations of the ‘sustainable city’, here understood as a city prioritising explicitly one or several environmental sustainability objectives. The most prominent visions of the sustainable city include the ‘Sustainable city’, the ‘Smart city’, the ‘Eco-city’, the ‘Low-carbon city’, the ‘Green city’, the ‘Resilient city’ and the ‘Circular city’ (de Jong et al., 2015; Fu and Zhang, 2017). However, we observe that the visions of the ‘just city’ consider only in a limited way environmental sustainability objectives and that, conversely, visions of the ‘sustainable city’ take little account of the imperatives of social justice (Fransolet et al., 2023).

Considering this gap between the visions of the ‘just city’ and those of the ‘sustainable city’, the main objective of this research is to explore urban visions that explicitly combine social justice and environmental sustainability objectives. More specifically, it aims at 1) outlining contrasting visions of a just and sustainable city in Brussels-capital Region, at 2) identifying the actors who support these visions, and 3) highlighting the areas of consensus and debate on the issue. With that aim in mind, we conducted a survey of Brussels’ stakeholders based on a Q-methodology. This method is indeed particularly well-suited to understanding the plurality of perspectives on a topic in a structured way, through the identification of ideal-typical visions. The following will therefore present the application of the Q-methodology for mapping different conceptions of a just and sustainable city in Brussels-Capital Region.

After presenting the framework of the Q-methodology, we demonstrate its implementation and the analysis of the data leading to the identification of three contrasted visions of a just and sustainable city in Brussels-Capital Region (Section 2). Subsequently, the results will be presented to depict the main features of each vision that was identified as well as the areas of consensus and debate between these visions (Section 3). Finally, these results will be discussed, and a conclusion leading to avenues for future research will finalise the report (Section 4).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Introduction to Q-Methodology

To identify contrasting visions of a just and sustainable city in Brussels-Capital-Region, we have conducted a Q-Survey of stakeholders. The Q-methodology (Watts & Stenner, 2005; Barry & Proops, 1990) consists in a statistically supported survey method that allows one to understand the diversity of perspectives on a topic within a group. As there are as many perspectives as survey respondents, this method aims at highlighting, in a structured and interpretable way, similarities and differences in the perceptions of respondents in relation to the subject of the study (Barry & Proops, 1999). It aims at identifying ideal-typical perspectives on the topic and at pointing to the groups of respondents who share these perspectives.

This method, which was developed in the field of psychology in the 1930s (Barry & Proops, 1999), has since the 1990s been increasingly used in other fields (Brown & al., 2015), including environmental sustainability research (Sneegas et al., 2021). The growing popularity of Q-methodology in environmental sustainability research can be explained by the adequacy of this method to analyse social phenomena that generate conflicts (Barry & Proops, 1999).

A Q-Survey is typically conducted in five main steps, starting with the identification of the population to be surveyed and the construction of the sample ('Q-Sample'). This survey method does not require many respondents (Cools & al., 2012; ten Klooster & al., 2008; Barry & Proops, 1999), since a statistical analysis with twelve participants can provide significant results (Barry & Proops, 1999). Another preliminary step consists in identifying the field of discourse to study and to formulate a list of statements that is supposed to cover all the possible perspectives on the topic. These statements are usually defined based on desk research and/or exploratory interviews (Davies & Hodge, 2007). Once the list of statements is completed, a selection is made so as to keep a manageable number of items for the survey, i.e., usually between 40 to 80 statements (Zabala & al., 2018; Watts & Stenner, 2005; Cools & al., 2012) ('Q-Set'). These statements are then submitted to the respondents who are invited to classify them in a quasi-normal distribution grid. In this grid, the statements are usually ranked according to the degree of agreement, with or without a maximum number of items per box depending on whether it is a forced or free distribution (Watts & Stenner, 2005). At the end of the sorting process, one gets a 'Q-Sort' for each participant, namely, all the items ranked against each other (Lefin & Boulanger 2010). The Q-Survey can be done either through interviews or online surveys. It often includes post-sorting questions, which notably aim to understand the reasons behind respondents' rankings and to identify important elements not covered by the statements. The data collected through the Q-Survey is processed through principal component analysis. This analysis leads to the identification of factors, which corresponds to 'typical Q-Sorts' allowing us to grasp "the common essence of several similar individual Q-Sorts" (Lefin & Boulanger 2010, p. 15, personal translation). In other words, the factors constitute ideal-typical perspectives on the topic shared by several respondents. Theoretically, they are not formulated as such by any respondent. In our research one factor corresponds to one specific vision of a just and sustainable city. The last step of the Q-Survey consists in describing and interpreting the results (Cools & al., 2012; Lefin & Boulanger, 2010; Davies & Hodge, 2007; Barry & Proops, 1999). The responses to the post-sorting questions can be useful for this final step.

2.2. Conduct of the Q-Methodology Survey

2.2.1 Construction of the Sample (Q-Sample)

The Q-Sample included Brussels' stakeholders, here understood as people involved in a professional capacity in areas related to social justice and/or environmental sustainability in the Brussels-Capital

Region. They are notably members of NGOs, advisory councils, trade unions, business federations, administrations, and citizen movements active in social and/or ecological policies.

A list of stakeholders to be invited to take part in the survey has been drawn up through a purposive sampling approach. This list has been elaborated in such a way as to cover all possible points of view on the just and sustainable city in Brussels. By this way, a list of 354 people to contact has been compiled.

2.2.2 Formulation of the Statements (Q-Set)

To formulate a set of statements intended to cover all possible perspectives on what a just and sustainable city should look like in Brussels (i.e., Q-Set), we conducted a documentary research and exploratory interviews.

A first list of statements reflecting possible dimensions of a just and sustainable city was formulated based on the review of the visions of ‘just city’ and ‘sustainable city’ conceptualised in the academic field previously carried out as part of the COGITO Project (see Fransolet et al., 2023). This review includes the ‘just city’ visions that inspired and have been inspired by Susan Fainstein’s 2010 contribution of the same name, i.e., *Social Justice and the City* (Harvey, 1973), *Justice and the Politics of Difference* (Young, 1990), *Towards Cosmopolis: Planning for Multicultural Cities* (Sandercock, 1997), *Planning in the Face of Power* (Forester, 1988), *Seeking Spatial Justice* (Soja, 2010), and *The Good City: In Defense of Utopian Thinking* (Friedmann, 2000). As for the visions of the ‘sustainable city’ reviewed, they correspond to the main visions identified based on the bibliometric analyses of concepts promoting urban sustainable transitions carried out by de Jong et al. (2015) and Fu and Zhang (2017): the ‘Sustainable city’, the ‘Smart city’, the ‘Eco-city’, the ‘Low-carbon city’, the ‘Green city’, the ‘Resilient city’ and the ‘Circular city’. For each ‘just city’ and ‘sustainable city’ vision selected, we have summarised their main characteristics and analysed if and how they integrate environmental sustainability and social justice objectives. With that aim in mind, we used an analytical framework grasping the main distributive, procedural and recognitional justice dimensions considered in urban, environmental, climate and energy justice scholarships³. Distributive justice concerns the fair allocation of environmental goods and bads, procedural justice focuses on fair decision-making processes on environmental issues, and recognitional justice emphasises recognizing and valuing the perspectives of marginalised groups in the social and political realms (Schlosberg, 2007). Such analysis enabled us to identify different possible dimensions of a just and sustainable city. On this basis, we defined a preliminary list of statements, with each statement reflecting one specific dimension of a just and sustainable city.

This list was supplemented by an analysis of the main relevant visions, strategies, and plans for the BCR. This analysis covers the Regional Sustainable Development Plan (PRDD), the regional economic transition strategy (SRTE), GO4Brussels 2030, Good Food 2, Good Move and the Nature Plan. We have analysed if and how they incorporate elements characteristic of a just and sustainable city. To do so, we used the analytical framework comprehending the different dimensions of justice considered in urban, environmental, climate and energy justice scholarships previously evoked. This analysis of regional policy documents led to the identification of dimensions of just urban sustainabilities that were not included in the visions of ‘just city’ and ‘sustainable city’ conceptualised in the academic field we reviewed, which allowed us to complete the list of statements.

The set of statements identified with documentary research was finally consolidated based on four exploratory interviews with relevant Brussels’ stakeholders conducted in October 2023. These interviews, which aimed to cover the broadest possible spectrum of perspectives on the just and

³ The combination of these four scholarships provides a comprehensive conceptual framework for just urban transitions (Hughes and Hoffmann, 2019), here understood as transitions to a just and sustainable city.

sustainable city in the BCR, were carried out with representatives of a sectoral business federations, a trade union, a regional public administration, and an association of local entities.

The documentary research and the exploratory interviews led to the formulation of 108 statements. To ensure that the questionnaire was not too long, we strived for reducing the number of statements as much as we could, while remaining as exhaustive as possible. Among 108 statements, 42 were selected jointly by the research team. The table hereunder presents the Q-Set with the 42 final statements translated in English⁴ (Table 1).

Table 1. The Q-Set with the 42 final statements translated in English

REF	Statements
1	Brussels becomes a territory where differences, diversity and multiculturalism are recognized and taken into account in urban planning processes.
2	Brussels becomes a territory where green spaces and infrastructure are equitably distributed across the urban territory.
3	Brussels becomes a territory where access to all forms of mobility is affordable and fairly distributed among all groups of residents.
4	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to decent and affordable housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
5	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to healthy food is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
6	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to health equipment is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
7	Brussels becomes a territory where access to digital goods and services is guaranteed for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.
8	Brussels becomes a territory where all social groups affected by urban policies participate in an informed and effective manner in decision-making processes.
9	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to renewable energy production systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
10	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to energy-efficient housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
11	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to an ecological individual vehicle is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of one today.
12	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to soft mobility infrastructure and services is guaranteed to all residents (e.g. public transport, cycling), in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
13	Brussels continues to evolve within the framework of a capitalist system.
14	Brussels becomes a territory where groups of residents act collectively in large-scale movements to radically transform urban spaces.
15	Brussels becomes a territory where power within political institutions is in the hands of historically dominated and marginalised populations.
16	Brussels becomes a territory where decision-making is organised through citizen assemblies and other horizontal processes instead of current political institutions.
17	Brussels becomes, in its entirety, a mixed-use territory guaranteeing all residents easy access to all residential and socio-economic activities (housing, offices, shops, parks, etc.).
18	Brussels becomes a territory where the offer of public services is significant and effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of them today.
19	Brussels becomes a territory where all activities collectively considered unsustainable have disappeared.
20	Brussels becomes a territory that gives priority to the interests of small, locally rooted businesses rather than those of large corporations.

⁴ The survey was conducted in French. A list with the statements in the original language can be consulted in Appendix 1.

21	Brussels becomes a territory which retains areas with low social and cultural diversity and which prevents all forms of discrimination.
22	Brussels becomes a territory where decent, quality work in the green economy is effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
23	Brussels becomes a high-density territory which allows quick, easy and safe access to amenities and services.
24	Brussels becomes a territory that limits the consumption of goods and services collectively considered non-essential (luxury, waste, etc.).
25	Brussels becomes a territory that reduces resource use and waste production through technological innovation.
26	Brussels becomes a city that is developing a sufficient and quality social housing supply, in particular by repurposing part of its green spaces.
27	Brussels becomes a resilient territory where all residents are protected from environmental risks (floods, heat waves, pollution, etc.), particularly the most vulnerable (residents of dense areas, elderly people, etc.).
28	Brussels becomes a territory that preserves and deploys vegetation networks and urban green infrastructure, in order to guarantee all forms of nature and their benefits for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.
29	Brussels becomes a territory that reduces the use of resources and the production of waste through social innovation (resource centres, food centres, Repair Café...).
30	Brussels becomes a territory where effective participation in food production and distribution systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today (collective garden, cooperative, food belt, etc.).
31	Brussels becomes a territory where all food is produced locally (Belgium and neighbouring regions).
32	Brussels becomes a competitive territory through the development of its leadership in the green economy.
33	Brussels becomes a territory providing many green jobs.
34	Brussels becomes a territory that guarantees an adequate level of training for workers to meet labour needs in the green economy.
35	Brussels becomes a territory where time devoted to work is severely limited.
36	Brussels becomes a territory where digital technology plays an important role in the deployment of ecological modes of production and consumptions.
37	Brussels becomes a territory where all forms of domination and marginalisation have been annihilated (sexism, classism, colonialism, speciesism, etc.).
38	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to a decent minimum income is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
39	Brussels becomes a territory where an income and assets ceiling is established.
40	Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm neighbouring regions.
41	Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities contribute to reducing north/south inequalities.
42	Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm future generations.

2.2.3 Data Collection (Q-Survey)

The data were collected through an online questionnaire supported by the [QMethodSoftware](#).

The survey started with introduction questions aimed at apprehending what type of organisation the respondents are active in and the area in which they work (see Appendix 2).

Subsequently, the 42 statements on the just and sustainable city were presented one by one in the same order for all respondents. The latter were invited to pre-sort the statements by stating whether they find it desirable, non-desirable or neutral.

The respondents were then asked to classify the statements more finely into a ranking grid according to their degree of desirability. This classification involved a forced distribution, where the respondents

must place a defined number of statements in each ranking position. As illustrated in the following figure (Figure 2), three statements had to be placed under both extremities “-4” (Least desirable) and “+4” (Most desirable), four statements under both columns “-3” and “+3”, five statements under the columns “-2” and “+2”, six statements under the columns “-1” and “+1”, and six statements under the column “0”. We choose a forced distribution rather than a free distribution to encourage respondents to position themselves in relation to each statement and to establish priorities between them.

Figure 2. The Q-sorting distribution

At the end of this stage, we obtained for each respondent, a Q-sort, which corresponds to the final classification of the 42 statements into the ranking grid.

The Q-Survey ended with an optional post-sorting questionnaire in which the respondents were invited to explain the ranking of statements to which they had assigned an extreme score (-4 or +4) and to indicate if important elements of their vision of a just and sustainable city were not included in the statements they classified. They were finally asked to identify key policy(ies) to be implemented to ensure the transition towards a just and sustainable in the BCR (see Appendix 2).

Invitations to participate in the Q-Survey were sent by email to the 354 stakeholders identified (see section 2.2.1), and a reminder was emailed halfway through the survey. This survey took place between the 11 January 2024 and the 11 February 2024. In total, 32 people completed the Q-Survey, which makes it possible to carry out a statistical analysis with significant results (Barry & Proops, 1999). The questionnaire was completed by representatives of administration or other public organisations, non-governmental organisations (NGOs), citizen movements, business federations, trade unions and two people involved in other types of organisations. The table below provides an overview of the distribution of the respondents per category of stakeholder (Table 2).

Table 2. Distribution of the respondents per category of stakeholder

Category of stakeholder	Number of respondents
Administration and other public organisations (ADM)	12
NGO or association (NGO)	10
Business Federation (FED)	4
Trade union (TRA)	3
Citizen movement (CYT)	1

Other (OTH)	2
TOTAL	32

2.2.4 Data Analysis

After having gathered the ranking of the 42 statements made by each respondent or ‘Q-sorts’, we have used the [Ken-Q Analysis](#) tool to analyse these data. As previously explained (see section 2.1), the objective of this statistical analysis was to identify ‘factors’, which represent a ‘typical Q-Sort’ reflecting a perspective on what a just and sustainable city should look like shared by several respondents. The analysis of the data was performed in two main steps: A principal component analysis (PCA), followed by a varimax rotation.

a) Principal Component Analysis

As a first step of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA), we obtained the matrix of correlations between the Q sorts. (Table 3). Here the Q-Sorts of the respondents are compared with those of the other respondents. A perfect positive correlation would be 100 while a perfect negative correlation would be presented as a -100. The responses of two participants would be considered significant correlated when their number is higher than 35 or 44⁵.

⁵ 2 or $2,5 * 100/\sqrt{N}$ with N= Number of respondents

Table 3. Matrix of correlations between the Q sorts

Participant	FED1	NGO1	ADM1	TRA3	ADM9	NGO8	ADM6	CYT1	TRA2	NGO2	ADM4	NGO4	OTH2	ADM5	NGO3	FED3	ADM1	ADM2	NGO5	OTH1	NGO7	FED4	ADM1	NGO1	NGO9	TRA1	ADM3	NGO6	ADM8	ADM1	ADM7	FED2
FED1	100	32	35	50	29	30	5	42	66	21	22	12	33	25	9	36	26	24	36	33	35	46	38	51	30	59	34	12	28	48	14	8
NGO1	32	100	40	33	10	15	3	49	37	3	14	46	35	8	32	-2	34	34	42	40	26	53	25	28	12	35	48	41	53	9	25	4
ADM11	35	40	100	32	29	29	-12	45	65	-13	6	31	32	6	17	25	40	66	35	55	52	43	55	33	23	39	49	30	58	44	29	-5
TRA3	50	33	32	100	30	22	0	33	42	42	19	12	33	7	15	35	12	29	34	24	25	19	47	54	20	59	40	-9	33	45	12	-6
ADM9	29	10	29	30	100	46	8	34	40	19	-2	-13	44	-19	11	17	0	53	25	38	32	33	52	30	34	18	38	-13	24	27	2	-6
NGO8	30	15	29	22	46	100	6	52	42	17	30	0	32	-14	1	30	13	28	33	35	54	45	53	50	28	33	47	23	37	32	22	11
ADM6	5	3	-12	0	8	6	100	1	19	-21	25	4	-5	-7	-5	38	6	-25	5	-32	-5	13	1	14	12	1	11	7	-25	18	-2	62
CYT1	42	49	45	33	34	52	1	100	47	20	37	24	44	1	17	37	35	44	52	47	64	50	40	50	29	22	69	17	56	29	27	6
TRA2	66	37	65	42	40	42	19	47	100	4	13	23	34	18	20	46	25	36	43	41	43	63	65	55	46	45	47	19	31	57	17	21
NGO2	21	3	-13	42	19	17	-21	20	4	100	-20	-20	38	-5	-6	9	-25	1	6	-2	-3	20	30	27	29	33	31	-14	14	28	-5	-14
ADM4	22	14	6	19	-2	30	25	37	13	-20	100	11	-19	-9	-1	32	37	-6	23	-3	29	19	4	35	-9	-8	21	25	-1	31	26	33
NGO4	12	46	31	12	-13	0	4	24	23	-20	11	100	-1	-1	24	-10	37	31	38	26	28	31	23	35	2	22	14	31	41	-7	34	-5
OTH2	33	35	32	33	44	32	-5	44	34	38	-19	-1	100	1	17	4	10	52	25	40	35	37	42	25	13	37	44	17	49	21	-8	-9
ADM5	25	8	6	7	-19	-14	-7	1	18	-5	-9	-1	1	100	-9	4	-18	-8	-23	-7	4	-1	-3	-12	-5	12	-7	-19	4	-6	-6	18
NGO3	9	32	17	15	11	1	-5	17	20	-6	-1	24	17	-9	100	-2	17	27	15	35	4	17	4	29	-18	11	20	8	27	5	14	-5
FED3	36	-2	25	35	17	30	38	37	46	9	32	-10	4	4	-2	100	25	3	20	-3	25	27	30	50	40	18	49	1	9	48	32	54
ADM12	26	34	40	12	0	13	6	35	25	-25	37	37	10	-18	17	25	100	38	48	12	32	20	30	37	6	10	35	44	32	41	23	14
ADM2	24	34	66	29	53	28	-25	44	36	1	-6	31	52	-8	27	3	38	100	42	61	44	22	51	35	10	30	38	23	66	18	24	-12
NGO5	36	42	35	34	25	33	5	52	43	6	23	38	25	-23	15	20	48	42	100	26	42	35	45	40	39	34	45	38	35	32	10	-11
OTH1	33	40	55	24	38	35	-32	47	41	-2	-3	26	40	-7	35	-3	12	61	26	100	57	40	41	29	14	23	39	10	65	-5	27	-36
NGO7	35	26	52	25	32	54	-5	64	43	-3	29	28	35	4	4	25	32	44	42	57	100	52	50	40	23	16	40	13	60	25	20	-5
FED4	46	53	43	19	33	45	13	50	63	20	19	31	37	-1	17	27	20	22	35	40	52	100	39	42	33	20	56	22	37	30	24	19
ADM10	38	25	55	47	52	53	1	40	65	30	4	23	42	-3	4	30	30	51	45	41	50	39	100	57	51	51	54	11	54	60	23	-3
NGO10	51	28	33	54	30	50	14	50	55	27	35	35	25	-12	29	50	37	35	40	29	40	42	57	100	35	36	50	26	39	48	25	27
NGO9	30	12	23	20	34	28	12	29	46	29	-9	2	13	-5	-18	40	6	10	39	14	23	33	51	35	100	25	36	-3	15	35	24	1
TRA1	59	35	39	59	18	33	1	22	45	33	-8	22	37	12	11	18	10	30	34	23	16	20	51	36	25	100	30	13	37	43	11	0
ADM3	34	48	49	40	38	47	11	69	47	31	21	14	44	-7	20	49	35	38	45	39	40	56	54	50	36	30	100	19	54	42	31	16
NGO6	12	41	30	-9	-13	23	7	17	19	-14	25	31	17	-19	8	1	44	23	38	10	13	22	11	26	-3	13	19	100	24	20	10	14
ADM8	28	53	58	33	24	37	-25	56	31	14	-1	41	49	4	27	9	32	66	35	65	60	37	54	39	15	37	54	24	100	12	48	-10
ADM1	48	9	44	45	27	32	18	29	57	28	31	-7	21	-6	5	48	41	18	32	-5	25	30	60	48	35	43	42	20	12	100	17	23
ADM7	14	25	29	12	2	22	-2	27	17	-5	26	34	-8	-6	14	32	23	24	10	27	20	24	23	25	24	11	31	10	48	17	100	5
FED2	8	4	-5	-6	-6	11	62	6	21	-14	33	-5	-9	18	-5	54	14	-12	-11	-36	-5	19	-3	27	1	0	16	14	-10	23	5	100

Based on this matrix, the PCA extracted eight factors reflecting eight visions of the just and sustainable city shared by several respondents. The values in the matrix below represent the correlation between each of these factors and each Q-sort (Table 4). A perfect positive correlation would be 1 and a perfect negative correlation would be -1. For each factor, the eigenvalue – i.e., the sum of the Q-sorts' correlations with the factor reflecting “relative contribution of a factor to the explanation of the total variance in the matrix” (Cools, et al., 2012) – and the percentage contribution to variance are indicated at the bottom of the matrix.

Table 4. Matrix showing the correlation of the eight factors with the Q-Sorts

Unrotated Factor Matrix									
Number	Participant	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 4	Factor 5	Factor 6	Factor 7	Factor 8
1	FED1	0.6377	0.1907	-0.1787	0.3731	0.0861	-0.0416	-0.038	-0.0325
2	NGO1	0.5739	-0.2279	0.3075	0.3319	-0.0041	0.3393	0.1503	0.2325
3	ADM11	0.7121	-0.2062	0.1306	0.0819	0.1486	-0.241	-0.3465	-0.0718
4	TRA3	0.5731	0.0942	-0.3372	0.342	-0.1822	-0.1002	0.2383	-0.279
5	ADM9	0.5043	-0.0508	-0.4147	-0.41	0.0522	0.1526	-0.2614	-0.1769
6	NGO8	0.6132	0.134	-0.1105	-0.4129	0.0601	0.0864	0.0543	0.0089
7	ADM6	0.0408	0.6747	0.1912	-0.0119	0.0656	0.3216	-0.1967	0.0812
8	CYT1	0.7503	-0.009	0.0882	-0.1966	0.1472	0.1497	0.2517	0.0261
9	TRA2	0.7664	0.2156	-0.0844	0.1896	0.2018	-0.0297	-0.3177	0.0654
10	NGO2	0.2241	0.0322	-0.6841	0.0624	-0.2914	0.1619	0.4508	0.1218
11	ADM4	0.262	0.4581	0.4709	-0.1785	-0.0119	-0.0604	0.2637	-0.2397
12	NGO4	0.3677	-0.2548	0.541	0.293	-0.0759	-0.1167	0.093	0.2547
13	OTH2	0.5427	-0.2753	-0.3387	0.0055	-0.03	0.473	-0.1315	-0.0474
14	ADM5	-0.0331	0.0444	-0.1252	0.567	0.6208	-0.0655	-0.0534	0.0397
15	NGO3	0.2637	-0.2689	0.2139	0.184	-0.0443	0.3035	0.1258	-0.4594
16	FED3	0.4494	0.6687	-0.034	-0.078	0.1733	-0.1522	0.0983	-0.1367
17	ADM12	0.4746	0.0803	0.5455	-0.0016	-0.3148	-0.1544	-0.1555	-0.1328
18	ADM2	0.6421	-0.47	0.0363	-0.0991	-0.0334	-0.0539	-0.2584	-0.2574
19	NGO5	0.634	-0.0279	0.1751	-0.0608	-0.4069	-0.0157	-0.0867	0.2413
20	OTH1	0.5962	-0.5748	0.0048	-0.1457	0.2622	-0.0238	0.0156	-0.0844
21	NGO7	0.6749	-0.1354	0.1086	-0.2884	0.2949	-0.1062	-0.0225	0.0384
22	FED4	0.6681	0.0804	0.0671	-0.0477	0.2402	0.2995	0.0566	0.3233
23	ADM10	0.7709	0.0178	-0.2689	-0.0665	-0.1076	-0.2242	-0.1742	0.0583
24	NGO10	0.7226	0.2715	0.032	0.0263	-0.1597	0.0027	0.1917	-0.1702
25	NGO9	0.4511	0.2475	-0.3302	-0.154	-0.0356	-0.273	-0.0322	0.5333
26	TRA1	0.5541	0.0031	-0.3026	0.5061	-0.2062	-0.0632	-0.0454	0.005
27	ADM3	0.7562	0.1061	-0.0311	-0.1421	0.021	0.1837	0.2186	0.0383
28	NGO6	0.319	-0.0089	0.5299	0.0512	-0.3645	0.2133	-0.1893	0.1877
29	ADM8	0.7056	-0.4523	0.1067	0.0111	0.1357	-0.0562	0.1886	-0.0153
30	ADM1	0.5701	0.4727	-0.1601	0.0832	-0.2802	-0.1988	-0.1752	-0.1757
31	ADM7	0.3795	-0.001	0.2939	-0.0701	0.1782	-0.4294	0.4302	0.0241
32	FED2	0.0804	0.7227	0.2552	0.0915	0.2537	0.2728	-0.0747	-0.0972
	Eigenvalues	9.7458	3.2153	2.7428	1.7177	1.5313	1.3673	1.3153	1.2015
	% Explained variance	30	10	9	5	5	4	4	4

Based on this matrix, we have selected, among the eight factors, those that were significant. A factor can be counted as significant if it meets the following two conditions. The first condition is that the factor's eigenvalue is greater than 1 and the second condition is that minimum two Q-Sorts are correlated significantly with the factor. A Q-sort and a factor can be considered as significantly correlated if the correlation between them is at least 0,5 and the Q-Sort's correlation with the other factors is less than 0,4 (Cools, et al., 2012). Factors 1, 2, and 3 meet these conditions and are thus considered significant. These three significant factors were to be kept in the further analysis.

b) Factor Rotation

After having selected the three significant factors, we have rotated them to get the final set of factors. The factor rotation aims at adapting the selected factors in such a way that they yield the highest possible explained variance possible. To do so, we have used the Varimax rotation, i.e., the objective⁶ rotation tool included in the Ken-Q Analysis software.

The varimax rotation enabled us to obtain the following matrix (Table 5). It includes the final set of factors and their correlation with the different Q-Sorts. By summing up each column we can calculate the eigenvalues of each factor. When comparing the eigenvalues of each factor with the others, we can determine the explained variance by each factor. We can see that the Factors 1, 2, and 3 explain a variance of 24%, 10%, and 15%, respectively, thus together accounting for 49% of the variance in the responses given (Table 5).

Table 5. Matrix showing the correlation of the three selected factors with the Q-Sorts (the significant correlations are highlighted in yellow)

Factor Matrix with Defining Sorts Flagged				
Statement Number	Q-Sort	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
1	FED1	0.6601	0.1356	0.1447
2	NGO1	0.2864	-0.0843	0.6218
3	ADM11	0.4973	-0.1225	0.5517
4	TRA3	0.6713	-0.0131	0.0168
5	ADM9	0.6291	-0.1784	-0.0349
6	NGO8	0.5949	0.1062	0.2027
7	ADM6	0.0482	0.6995	-0.0424
8	CYT1	0.584	0.0479	0.4769
9	TRA2	0.7238	0.1967	0.2799
10	NGO2	0.5461	-0.2061	-0.4226
11	ADM4	0.0541	0.6041	0.3638
12	NGO4	-0.0118	-0.0332	0.7011
13	OTH2	0.585	-0.3597	0.1161
14	ADM5	0.044	-0.0042	-0.1296
15	NGO3	0.0668	-0.1662	0.3943
16	FED3	0.5067	0.6273	0.0045
17	ADM12	0.1316	0.2849	0.6563
18	ADM2	0.4431	-0.4047	0.5238
19	NGO5	0.4384	0.0573	0.4878
20	OTH1	0.4033	-0.5153	0.5076
21	NGO7	0.4891	-0.0654	0.4921
22	FED4	0.5407	0.1211	0.3877
23	ADM10	0.7897	-0.0535	0.201
24	NGO10	0.6364	0.2889	0.3293
25	NGO9	0.5906	0.1285	-0.0922
26	TRA1	0.6223	-0.0865	0.0623
27	ADM3	0.6696	0.1131	0.3506
28	NGO6	-0.0061	0.191	0.5883
29	ADM8	0.4631	-0.361	0.6074
30	ADM1	0.6406	0.4033	0.0335
31	ADM7	0.1676	0.1163	0.4345
32	FED2	0.0565	0.7684	0.0138
% Explained variance		24	10	15

⁶ Objective rotation differs from theoretical rotation. In the first case, the factors are rotated automatically by the programme, whereas in the second, the user adjusts the factors.

In this matrix, the Q-sorts correlated significantly with each factor are highlighted in yellow. These significant correlations were automatically identified by the programme according to the criteria outlined previously. To these, we added a manually identified correlation that was just below the selection threshold set by the program, i.e., the correlation between the Q-sorts OTH1 and Factor 3.

Finally, the following table shows how each factor correlates with the other factors (Table 6). A higher correlation can be observed between Factors 1 (the 'Foundational City') and 3 (the 'Exnovation City'). This indicates that these two factors share more in common than Factor 2 (the 'Smart City'). This latter is closer to Factor 1 than Factor 3.

Table 6. Matrix of the correlation scores between the factors

Factor score correlations			
	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3
Factor 1	1	0,2432	0,5233
Factor 2	0,2432	1	0,09
Factor 3	0,5233	0,09	1

3. Results

3.1. Most and Least Desirable Statements

Before delving into the characterisation of the three factors identified through statistical analysis, we identify the statements perceived as most and least desirable. The table below displays the score that each respondent has attributed to each statement. The total score obtained by each statement is indicated in the last line of the table. The five lowest and highest total scores are respectively highlighted in red and green (Table 7).

Table 7. Participants' ranking for each statement with the total score

Participant	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8	S9	S10	S11	S12	S13	S14	S15	S16	S17	S18	S19	S20	S21	S22	S23	S24	S25	S26	S27	S28	S29	S30	S31	S32	S33	S34	S35	S36	S37	S38	S39	S40	S41	S42
ADM9	-1	-1	-3	1	-2	-1	1	2	2	3	-4	1	-4	-1	0	1	-2	1	0	-3	-2	3	-2	-4	-4	-1	4	-2	2	3	-1	1	0	2	0	-3	3	4	4	0	0	2
FED1	0	2	3	2	1	0	-3	-1	1	1	-4	2	-4	-2	-4	3	4	3	-2	-1	-3	0	-1	-1	-4	3	1	0	2	-1	1	-2	-1	4	1	-3	0	2	-3	-2	0	4
TRA3	0	-1	2	2	0	0	-3	0	1	3	-4	4	-4	3	-1	-3	2	4	-2	-2	-4	4	1	-2	0	3	-1	3	1	0	-1	-2	-1	-2	2	-3	-1	1	1	-3	1	2
NGO2	2	-2	1	3	1	0	1	2	-2	2	-4	-1	-4	0	3	-1	3	3	-4	-1	1	-2	0	-1	-1	4	0	1	-3	0	-1	-4	-3	-3	2	-2	4	2	4	-3	-2	1
NGO4	1	0	2	0	1	0	-1	-4	3	-1	-4	3	-4	-2	-3	0	2	-1	3	4	1	3	-4	4	2	-3	-2	4	-1	-1	2	1	-2	-1	-2	-3	1	-2	0	2	1	0
NGO3	3	1	-1	4	0	0	-2	3	-1	-3	-4	-1	-4	-3	1	2	-2	1	3	4	-4	1	-4	-2	2	2	-3	2	1	3	-1	4	2	-2	0	-1	-2	0	-1	0	0	1
ADM2	-1	-1	-3	2	-1	0	-2	3	2	2	-4	2	-4	-2	-2	-2	-1	0	4	1	-1	1	-4	3	-3	-3	3	1	4	0	0	1	0	-1	1	-2	1	0	3	-4	2	4
NGO10	2	2	1	3	3	0	-2	-1	1	3	-4	1	-4	-1	-4	-2	0	4	-4	3	-2	0	-3	-3	1	-1	2	4	1	0	1	0	-2	0	-2	-3	-1	2	2	-1	-1	4
NGO9	3	3	0	3	4	0	0	-2	3	2	-4	2	-4	0	-1	-3	1	0	-2	-2	-1	-4	1	-1	-1	-1	4	-2	1	1	-3	-4	0	2	-1	-3	4	2	1	2	1	-3
CYT1	1	2	-1	4	2	1	-4	3	0	2	-4	1	-4	3	-1	3	0	0	0	-3	-2	-1	-2	1	-2	-4	2	4	0	1	3	-2	-2	-1	-3	-3	2	1	-1	0	-1	4
ADM4	-1	2	0	-1	1	1	-1	0	1	2	-4	-2	-4	4	-4	3	3	1	-2	0	-1	3	0	-2	1	-2	3	4	2	2	4	0	-1	-1	-4	0	-3	1	-4	-3	-3	-2
OTH2	-2	-2	-4	3	2	1	-3	2	-1	3	-4	1	-4	-2	1	2	-3	-1	-1	0	0	0	0	1	-3	0	-2	3	0	1	-1	-2	-1	2	4	-1	4	3	1	-4	2	4
ADM12	-2	4	-2	1	4	1	0	-2	2	0	-4	2	-4	-1	-3	0	-1	1	1	3	-3	2	0	2	-1	-3	2	4	3	-1	1	3	0	-2	-3	-2	0	-1	-4	-4	-1	1
NGO5	-1	2	-1	3	4	1	-4	1	4	3	-4	3	-4	-2	1	0	0	4	3	0	-2	2	-3	0	-1	-2	2	1	1	0	2	-3	-4	0	-3	-2	1	-1	-2	-1	2	-3
OTH1	0	0	-1	1	0	1	-3	2	0	-1	-4	1	-4	2	-3	4	-2	0	4	2	-3	-1	-3	3	-1	-2	2	-1	3	1	-1	-2	-2	0	4	-4	-2	2	3	1	1	3
ADM7	4	2	-1	-1	-2	1	3	1	2	-2	-4	4	-4	1	-3	-1	3	-4	2	2	-3	-2	-1	0	4	-2	3	2	1	-1	3	-3	1	0	0	0	0	1	-1	-2	-3	0
ADM6	-2	2	-2	-1	1	2	0	-1	0	1	-3	0	-4	-2	-4	-1	1	3	-2	-3	2	3	2	-4	4	-3	-3	0	0	1	-1	1	1	2	-3	4	3	3	-4	4	-1	0
ADM5	2	0	2	0	-4	2	-4	-3	-3	-3	-3	1	-4	1	1	0	2	-1	-2	-1	-1	3	4	-2	4	0	-2	1	2	0	1	0	2	-3	1	3	-1	-2	-1	-3	4	
FED3	1	3	0	1	2	2	3	2	0	2	-3	4	-4	-1	-2	-2	1	3	-3	-3	-2	-3	4	-4	1	-2	3	2	1	0	-1	-1	-1	0	-3	-1	-2	1	-4	0	0	4
NGO7	-2	2	0	-1	1	2	-3	1	-1	4	-3	3	-4	1	-2	3	-1	0	-1	2	-3	-1	1	3	-3	-4	1	0	3	4	4	-2	-2	0	-2	-3	0	-1	2	1	0	2
ADM8	2	1	0	0	1	2	-1	1	0	0	-3	3	-4	0	-2	-1	-3	-1	3	1	-4	-1	-3	4	-1	-2	-1	2	3	1	4	-3	-2	-2	2	-2	3	1	2	-3	0	4
ADM11	0	-1	2	2	2	3	-2	1	0	1	-3	3	-4	0	-3	-3	-2	0	3	1	-2	2	-1	4	-3	-4	4	-1	1	2	0	-1	3	1	1	-3	-1	-1	-2	-2	0	4
NGO8	1	0	-3	-2	2	3	0	4	2	3	-3	0	-3	4	-1	0	-2	3	-4	2	-3	-1	-3	-1	-4	-2	2	1	0	0	3	-1	-2	4	-1	-1	1	2	1	1	-2	1
FED4	0	-4	3	1	2	3	-1	2	1	2	-3	2	-3	-2	-3	4	0	0	-2	3	-3	-1	-1	1	0	-2	2	0	-1	3	0	-1	-2	1	-2	-4	4	4	-3	1	-1	1
TRA1	0	0	-1	2	2	3	0	-2	2	3	-2	2	-3	0	0	-3	4	4	-1	-1	-3	1	-4	2	-3	3	-3	-1	-1	-2	1	-2	1	1	4	-2	0	1	-2	-1	1	3
ADM3	1	0	0	3	4	3	1	2	-1	2	-2	2	-3	3	0	1	-2	2	2	0	-2	0	-1	-2	0	-3	1	1	1	-1	-1	-3	-1	-1	-3	-4	4	3	-2	-3	-2	4
ADM1	-1	1	-1	4	2	3	1	-1	-1	4	-2	2	-3	-1	-3	-3	1	3	-2	1	-2	2	1	-2	-4	3	4	2	0	2	0	-3	3	0	-2	0	0	0	-3	-2	-4	1
FED2	-1	0	0	-2	3	3	1	0	-2	2	-1	0	-1	-3	-4	-2	2	1	-3	-2	-1	-2	0	-3	2	-1	1	2	1	-1	0	4	1	-1	-4	4	3	2	-4	1	-1	3
NGO1	-2	0	3	4	1	4	-3	0	1	0	-1	1	-1	1	-3	2	-2	-1	2	-1	-4	1	-4	3	3	0	-1	2	-1	-2	2	1	0	-1	0	-3	4	3	-2	-2	2	-1
TRA2	0	-2	1	3	3	4	-3	0	0	-1	-1	3	2	-2	-4	-1	1	2	-1	0	-3	1	-1	-1	-3	0	4	1	1	2	-1	-2	1	4	-2	-3	0	2	-2	2	2	3
ADM10	-1	0	-3	3	3	4	1	-2	1	0	0	4	3	0	-2	-3	-1	3	-2	1	-2	2	-2	1	-3	0	3	0	2	2	0	-4	-1	1	-1	-3	2	1	4	-1	-2	2
NGO6	-3	1	1	1	4	4	-1	0	1	2	3	-4	4	-2	-2	-3	-3	-1	3	3	2	0	-2	2	1	0	2	3	0	-2	4	2	-4	3	0	0	-1	1	4	-2	-1	-1
Total	3	16	-6	48	47	53	-34	13	18	41	-94	49	-96	-6	-57	-6	3	36	-7	10	-60	11	-36	5	-26	-25	39	40	29	15	22	-28	-21	11	-23	-55	34	38	-22	-29	-6	56

3.1.1. Statements Rated as the Most Desirable

The table below displays the five statements with the highest total score, i.e., those deemed to be the most desirable on average (table 8). Those that score similarly on all three factors, and are therefore the subject of consensus, are shown in bold.

Table 8. Statements that received the highest total scores. Those obtaining a similar score in all three factors are indicated in bold.

REF	Statement	Score
42	Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm future generations.	+56
6	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to health equipment is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	+53
12	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to soft mobility infrastructure and services is guaranteed to all residents (e.g. public transport, cycling), in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	+49
4	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to decent and affordable housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	+48
5	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to healthy food is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	+47

Statement 42, which suggests that political decisions and economic activities of the BCR should not harm future generations, received the highest total score with +56. Nine participants ranked it with the highest score (+4) and four with the second highest category (+3). At the same time, nobody gave it the lowest score (-4) and only two the second lowest score (-3).

The statement which received the second highest cumulative score (+53) was the statement advocating for the fulfilment of effective access to health equipment to all Brussels' residents (6). Four people deemed it to be the most desirable (+4), and six people deemed it the second most desirable (+3). Interestingly, the lowest score that this statement received was -1 and only one participant allocated this score. As we will see later in the analysis, this statement is in fact the subject of a consensus between the three factors (see Section 3.3.1).

All three of the other statements with the highest scores also relate to guaranteeing effective access to essential goods and services for all. These include access to soft mobility infrastructure and services (e.g. public transport, cycling) (+49), decent and affordable housing (+48) and healthy food (+47). This latter is, just like the statement concerning effective access to health equipment, the subject of a consensus between the three factors (see Section 3.3.1).

3.1.2. Statements Rated as the Least Desirable

The table below presents the statements with the lowest overall score, i.e., the ones that were rated on average the least desirable (Table 9). The statements that received the lowest overall score were the statements 13, 11, 21, 15 and 36. Note that it does not necessarily mean that the statement is perceived as undesirable by the respondents. The forced distribution may in fact have forced some participants to assign negative scores to statements they considered desirable. This has been expressed by a respondent in the post-sorting questions: "for the + there wasn't enough room" (OTH 2). A lowest score for a statement therefore means above all that it is, on average, considered less desirable than the other statements.

Table 9. Statements that received the lowest total scores. Those obtaining a similar score in all three factors are indicated in bold.

REF	Statement	Score
13	Brussels continues to evolve within the framework of a capitalist system.	-96
11	Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to an ecological individual vehicle is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of one today.	-94
21	Brussels becomes a territory which retains areas with low social and cultural diversity and which prevents all forms of discrimination.	-60
15	Brussels becomes a territory where power within political institutions is in the hands of historically dominated and marginalised populations.	-57
36	Brussels becomes a territory where digital technology plays an important role in the deployment of ecological modes of production and consumption.	-55

The first two statements deemed the least desirable obtained a similar total score (-96 and -94), which is much more negative than that of the other three (-60, -57 and -55).

The first one was the statement in favour of a maintenance of the capitalist system (13). With a total score of -96 this statement has received 22 times the lowest score (-4), five times the second lowest score (-3) and only three positive scores (+2, +3, +4).

The statement that ranked the second lowest, was the statement advocating the guarantee of effective access to an ecological individual vehicle to all Brussels residents (11). With a total score of -94, fifteen people have ranked this statement the lowest score (-4), eight people the second lowest (-3) and only one person has given this statement a positive score (+3). Interestingly, it obtained a similar score for each of the three factors, which suggests a consensus on its lesser desirability (see Section 3.3.1).

3.2. Characterisation of the Three Factors

This section presents, for each factor, the vision of the just and sustainable city for Brussels they encapsulate, the Q-sorts that are significantly correlated with them, their composite Q-sorts, as well as their distinguishing statements.

To make it easier to communicate the factors, we have assigned to each of them a name reflecting their emblematic feature:

- Factor 1: The ‘**Foundational City**’
- Factor 2: The ‘**Smart City**’
- Factor 3: The ‘**Exnovation City**’

3.2.1. Factor 1: The ‘**Foundational City**’

a) **Vision of Just and Sustainable City associated with Factor 1**

The vision of the ‘**Foundational City**’ gives major priority to guaranteeing effective access to **decent minimum income** (S38, +3⁷) as well as **existential goods and services to all Brussels residents**, particularly those who are deprived today. These goods and services include access to **decent, affordable and energy-efficient housing** (S4, +4; S10, +3), public services (S18, +4), **soft mobility infrastructures and services** (e.g. public transports, cycling) (S12, +3), **healthy food** (S5, +3); **health equipment** (6, +2), and **adequate training in green jobs** (S32, +2). Factor 1 makes a point of providing these fundamental human needs for all without harming future generations (S42, +4). This factor also attaches a great importance to Brussels becoming a **resilient** territory where all inhabitants are

⁷ The first digit corresponds to the reference of the statement and the second one to the average score that the statement obtained for this factor.

protected from natural hazards, particularly the most vulnerable (S27, +2). Conversely, Factor 1 tends to place less importance on regional economic competitiveness (S32, -3). This de-prioritisation of economic objectives over intra- and intergenerational justice imperatives is reflected in the responses to the post-sorting questionnaire from the participants whose Q-sort is significantly correlated to Factor 1. One of them thus explains: "In my opinion, environmental and social struggles are linked. They include access to healthy housing, healthy food, the transport system, green spaces and health care, mobilising resources without compromising their regeneration or availability for the future. Generally speaking, I would tend to prioritise access to all of these things (...)"⁸ (FED 1). Another respondent states that "The protection of citizens against natural disasters, access to health, public services, access to housing, energy, food and training seem to me to be priorities." (TRA 2). Another again puts it this way: "The priorities are vital needs and living together" (FED 4).

The vision of a just and sustainable city of Factor 1 further promotes the **deployment of vegetation networks and urban green infrastructure, to guarantee all forms of nature and their benefits for all residents**, in particular those who are deprived of them today (S28, +2). However, this vision does not rule out converting some of the region's green spaces into social housing, to develop a sufficient and quality social housing supply (S26, 0). This involves a deprioritisation of achieving equitable distribution of green spaces and infrastructures (S2, 0) if the imperatives of providing affordable quality housing require it. In this regard, a representative of a business federation states that "In urban areas, it is not realistic to want a balance between green zone and exploited zone" (FED 4).

Factor 1 is further characterised by techno-pessimism, notably towards digital technologies (S36, -4; S11, -4; S25, -3; S7, -2). In this regard, a representative of eco-companies explains: "We will have no choice to go digital, which is good but must be thought about in a reasoned manner." (FED 4). A trade unionist further highlights the negative social impacts associated with the deployment of digital technologies: "I think that digital technology is not the miracle solution because it generates many negative effects (digital divide, social isolation, unequal relationships between customer and supplier, etc.). It is better to rehabilitate the human and the low tech." (TRA 2).

More fundamentally, the vision of a just and sustainable city associated with Factor 1 implies an overhaul of the capitalist system (S13, -4). Many of the responses to the post-sorting questions from participants associated with Factor 1 do indeed point in this direction: "The current capitalist system (-4) is not compatible with mitigating climate change, as well as many other problems related to the environment, health, social justice,..." (ADM 9); "The main problems of our society come from capitalist society" (ADM 3); "Capitalism is pushing towards our downfall" (NGO 9); or again "Capitalism brought us to where we are, let's try something else." (FED 4).

Finally, Factor 1 is not opposed to establishing an income and assets ceiling (S39, 0). In this respect, a member of an administration asserts that "A temporary solution [for mitigating climate change, as well as many other problems related to the environment, health, social justice (...)] would be to better redistribute riches (heritage, etc.)" (ADM 9).

We assigned the name '**Foundational City**' to this factor, as it echoes the concept of the 'foundational economy' (Bentham et al. 2013). In its essence, the concept of foundational economy stresses the importance of "the provision of everyday universal basics like food, housing, health services and transport within planetary limits" (Calafati et al. 2023, 1). By prioritising the fulfilment of fundamental needs of present generations without compromising those of future generations over economic objectives, Factor 1 fully resonates with this perspective.

b) Q-Sorts Significantly Correlated with Factor 1

Of the 34 collected Q-Sorts, 15 have a significant correlation with Factor 1 'Foundational City'. This is thus the factor with the highest number of significantly correlated Q-sorts. The following table

⁸ This is a personal translation of the answers to the questionnaire, which were all in French.

indicates the number of Q sorts significantly correlated with Factor 1 per category of stakeholder (Table 10).

Table 10. Number of Q sorts significantly correlated with Factor 1 per category of stakeholder

Category of stakeholder	Number of Q sorts significantly correlated with Factor 1
Administration and other public organisations	4
NGO or association	4
Business Federation	2
Trade union	3
Citizen movement	1
Other	1
TOTAL	15

When inspecting the affiliation of the participants who are associated with Factor 1, we can see that of the 12 participants in the study who work in administration and other public organisations, four are associated with Factor 1. More specifically, they are involved in energy, climate, energy efficiency; agricultural policies; social dialogue; climate change.

Moreover, of the 10 survey participants who are employed in non-governmental organisations or associations, four are significantly correlated with Factor 1. They are active in the areas of the right to housing and the city; circular construction; spokesperson for young people, responsible active critical and supportive citizenship (CRACS), citizenship; social services for personal assistance (prisoner rehabilitation).

All three people working for trade unions who filled out the questionnaire are associated with Factor 1. They work in the areas of environment; fair transition, taxation, the fight against poverty, mobility, the circular economy, defending vulnerable consumers; environmental information and awareness-raising for trade union members, just transition, energy and climate, energy insecurity, biodiversity.

The only person indicating in the questionnaire that they are working for a citizen movement is also associated with Factor 1. They are involved in the areas of spatial planning.

From the four participants that said they are working for a business federation, two are associated with Factor 1. They are involved with biodiversity and circular economy in the construction sector.

From the two people who indicated “other”, one is associated with Factor 1. They are involved with the help for litigants.

Appendix 3 illustrates the Q-Sorts of these respondents with their respective weight in the construction of Factor 1.

c) Composite Q-Sort of Factor 1

The figure below depicts the composite Q-sort of Factor 1 (Figure 3). This visual representation of the factor reflects the average ranking of the statements in the Q-Sorts significantly correlated to this factor⁹.

⁹ The statements marked in blue show the 11 statements with the lowest Z-Score variance.

Figure 3. Composite Q-sort for Factor 1

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
36. Brussels is becoming a territory where digital technology plays an important role in the deployment of ecological production and consumption methods.	19. Brussels is becoming a territory where all activities collectively considered unsustainable have disappeared.	** 24. Brussels is becoming a territory that limits the consumption of goods and services collectively considered non-essential (luxury, waste, etc.).	** 20. Brussels is becoming a territory that gives priority to the interests of small, locally rooted businesses rather than those of large corporations.	** 38. Brussels becomes a territory where an income and assets ceiling is established.	30. Buxelles is becoming a territory where effective participation in food production and distribution systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today (collective garden, cooperative, food belt, etc.).	6. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to health equipment is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	5. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to healthy food is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	** 4. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to decent and affordable housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
11. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to an ecological individual vehicle is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of one today.	21. Brussels is becoming a territory which retains areas with low social and cultural diversity and which prevents all forms of discrimination.	7. Brussels is becoming a territory where access to digital goods and services is guaranteed for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.	35. Brussels is becoming a territory where time devoted to work is severely limited.	1. Brussels is becoming a territory where differences, diversity and multiculturalism are recognized and taken into account in urban planning processes.	29. Brussels is becoming a territory that reduces the use of resources and the production of waste through social innovation (resource centers, food centers, Repair Café...)	* 27. Brussels is becoming a resilient territory where all residents are protected from environmental risks (floods, heat waves, pollution, etc.), particularly the most vulnerable (residents of dense areas, elderly people, etc.).	12. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to soft mobility infrastructure and services is guaranteed to all residents (e.g. public transport, cycling), in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	* 42. Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm future generations.
13. Brussels continues to evolve within the framework of a capitalist system.	** 25. Brussels is becoming a territory that reduces resource use and waste production through technological innovation.	* 40. Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm neighboring regions.	41. Brussels is becoming a territory whose political decisions and economic activities contribute to reducing north/south inequalities.	** 26. Brussels is becoming a city that is developing a sufficient and quality social housing supply, in particular by repurposing part of its green spaces.	* 9. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to renewable energy production systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	37. Brussels becomes a territory where all forms of domination and marginalization have been annihilated (sexism, classism, colonialism, speciesism, etc.).	10. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to energy-efficient housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	18. Brussels is becoming a territory where the offer of public services is significant and effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of them today.
	** 32. Brussels is becoming a competitive territory through the development of its leadership in the green economy.	** 23. Brussels is becoming a high-density territory which allows quick, easy and safe access to amenities and services.	3. Brussels is becoming a territory where access to all forms of mobility is affordable and fairly distributed among all groups of residents.	* 14. Brussels is becoming a territory where groups of residents act collectively in large-scale movements to radically transform urban spaces.	22. Brussels is becoming a territory where decent, quality work in the green economy is effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	* 34. Brussels is becoming a territory that guarantees an adequate level of training for workers to meet labor needs in the green economy.	38. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to a decent minimum income is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	
		* 15. Brussels is becoming a territory where power within political institutions is in the hands of historically dominated and marginalized populations.	16. Brussels is becoming a territory where decision-making is organized through citizen assemblies and other horizontal processes instead of current political institutions.	31. Brussels is becoming a territory where all food is produced locally (Belgium and neighboring regions).	** 17. Brussels is becoming, in its entirety, a mixed-use territory guaranteeing all residents easy access to all residential and socio-economic activities (housing, offices, shops, parks, etc.).	28. Brussels is becoming a territory that preserves and deploys vegetation networks and urban green infrastructure, in order to guarantee all forms of nature and their benefits for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.		
			33. Brussels is becoming a territory providing many green jobs.	** 2. Brussels is becoming a territory where green spaces and infrastructure are equitably distributed across the urban territory.	8. Brussels is becoming a territory where all social groups affected by urban policies participate in an informed and effective manner in decision-making processes.			

Legend

- * Distinguishing statement at $P < 0.05$
- ** Distinguishing statement at $P < 0.01$
- Z-score for the statement is higher than in all other factors
- ◄ Z-score for the statement is lower than in all other factors
- Consensus Statements

d) Distinguishing Statements of Factor 1

Each factor has distinguishing statements, i.e., statements that have an average score which is particularly high or low in comparison with the average score of the other factors. These statements are determined by analysing the Z-Scores of a statement's ranking in each factor¹⁰. The following table shows the distinguishing statements of Factor 1. The green cells highlight the average score that are particularly high compared with that of other factors, and the red cells, those that are particularly low (Table 11).

Table 11. Distinguishing statements of Factor 1

Statement Number	Factor 1	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 2	Factor 3	Factor 3
	Q-SV	Z-Score	Q-SV	Z-Score	Q-SV	Z-Score
4	4	1.55	-2	-0.541	2	0.921
42	4	1.47	2	0.844	1	0.405
27	2	1.09	0	0.4	1	0.339
34	2	0.66	-1	-0.01	-1	-0.342
9	1	0.4	-1	-0.3	2	0.969
17	1	0.23	2	0.967	-2	-0.583
39	0	0.17	-4	-2.247	-2	-1.025
26	0	0.12	-2	-1.069	-3	-1.187
14	0	0.07	-2	-0.601	-1	-0.575
2	0	-0.06	2	0.831	2	0.715
20	-1	-0.1	-3	-1.177	3	1.292
24	-2	-0.5	-3	-1.841	4	1.578
40	-2	-0.59	1	0.483	-2	-0.998
23	-2	-0.76	1	0.738	-4	-1.63
15	-2	-0.99	-4	-2.024	-3	-1.451
25	-3	-1.39	4	1.204	1	0.39
32	-3	-1.39	2	0.842	0	0.194

The distinguishing statements with higher scores of Factor 1 reflect the prioritisation of intra- and intergenerational justice objectives that characterises this factor:

Statement 4: Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to decent and affordable housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today. (+4)

Statement 42: Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm future generations. (+4)

They both achieve a ranking of +4 (Most desirable) in the composite Q-Sort of Factor 1 and their Z-Score is higher than in all other factors. These statements mirror the two main priorities of this factor, as they place particular emphasis on guaranteeing access to fundamental human needs for all Brussels' residents without harming future generations.

Factor 1 also stands out from the others by giving a higher score than other factors to the statement advocating for protecting all inhabitants of the region, particularly the most vulnerable, in the face of environmental risks:

¹⁰ A Z-Score indicates the relationship of a value to the mean. A Z-Score of 0 shows that the value is identical to the mean while a Z-Score of +1 shows that the value is one standard deviation higher than the mean. When placing the Z-Score of a statement in one factor in relation with the Z-Score of the same statement in the other factors, we can thus see if that statement has an exceptional rating in that factor. This distance between the Z-Scores can be determined by subtracting the Z-Score in one factor with the Z-Score of each other factor. For example, statement 4 has a Z-Score in Factor 1 of +1,55, in Factor 2 of -0,541, and Factor 3 of +0,921, the distance can then be determined by calculating (1,55-(-0,541)+1,55-0,921). A statement will be considered as distinguishing if this distance is >1 (see Appendix 6-8 for an overview about these statements for each factor).

Statement 27: Brussels becomes a resilient territory where all residents are protected from environmental risks (floods, heat waves, pollution, etc.), particularly the most vulnerable (residents of dense areas, elderly people, etc.). (+2)

Similarly, this factor places greater priority than others on guaranteeing adequate training of workers in green jobs:

Statement 34: Brussels becomes a territory that guarantees an adequate level of training for workers to meet labor needs in the green economy. (+2)

Factor 1 is also the only factor that does not have a negative average score for the statement in favour of introducing a cap on income and assets:

Statement 39: Brussels becomes a territory where an income and assets ceiling is established. (0)

In the same way, Factor 1 is the only one of the three factors that doesn't score negatively on the statement promoting the conversion of part of Brussels' green spaces into social housings to address the current shortage of quality affordable housing:

Statement 26: Brussels becomes a city that is developing a sufficient and quality social housing supply, in particular by repurposing part of its green spaces. (0)

As a result, the equitable distribution of green spaces is considered to be less of a priority for Factor 1 than for the other two factors:

Statement 2: Brussels becomes a territory where green spaces and infrastructure are equitably distributed across the urban territory. (0)

Factor 1 also distinguishes itself from other two factors by assigning higher - but still quite negative/neutral - average score to the following statements promoting procedural justice:

Statement 14: Brussels becomes a territory where groups of residents act collectively in large-scale movements to radically transform urban spaces. (0)

Statement 15: Brussels becomes a territory where power within political institutions is in the hands of historically dominated and marginalized populations. (-2)

Finally, the two following statements obtain a very negative score in Factor 1 – whereas they have a neutral or positive score in the other factors –, which reflects the de-prioritisation of economic development objectives and the techno-pessimism specific to this factor:

Statement 25: Brussels becomes a territory that reduces resource use and waste production through technological innovation. (-3)

Statement 32: Brussels becomes a competitive territory through the development of its leadership in the green economy. (-3)

3.2.2. Factor 2: The 'Smart City'

a) Vision of Just and Sustainable City associated with Factor 2

In the 'Smart City' vision, advances in technology (S25, +4), and notably digital (S36, +4), play a key role in ensuring the deployment of ecological modes of production and consumption. This ideal of a "green and digital economy" (FED 2) is evoked by a member of a business federation associated with Factor 2 in the responses to the post-sorting questions. Factor 2 further promotes the accessibility to eco-efficient technologies, notably by striving for guaranteeing effective access to energy-efficient housing (S10, +2) and digital goods and services for all Brussels residents (S7, +1), particularly those who are deprived of them today.

This technocentric vision of a just and sustainable city goes hand in hand with the advent of ‘green neoliberalism’ and ‘eco-capitalism’. Factor 2 indeed prioritises the region's economic competitiveness through the development of its leadership in the green economy (S32, +2), and supports a continuation of a capitalist system (S1, +1). In line with the neoliberalist approach, Factor 2 also tends to oppose public intervention aimed at regulating economic activities. It is thus unfavourable to the introduction of a ceiling on income and assets (39, -4), strong limits on working hours (S35, -4), limits on the consumption of goods and services collectively considered as non-essential (S24, -3), the purposive termination of all activities collectively considered unsustainable (S19, -3) and the prioritisation of the interests of small, locally rooted businesses over those of large corporations (S20, -3). The response to the post-sorting questionnaire of one representative of business federation whose Q-Sort is correlated with Factor 2 reflects this idea of promoting sustainable economic activities rather than regulating unsustainable ones: Considering “sustainable economic development” a priority, this respondent advocates for “promoting businesses that adopt sustainable practices, encourage innovation in green technologies and support start-ups focused on sustainability”, while “limiting political intervention” (FED 2). In the same vein, a member of administration argues in favour of “a broad promotion of the entrepreneurial spirit within the capital” (ADM 4).

In terms of urban planning, Factor 2 promotes the preservation and deployment of vegetation networks and urban green infrastructure, to guarantee all forms of nature and their benefits for all residents, particularly those who are deprived of them today (S28, +3). These green spaces should be equitably distributed across the urban territory (S2, +2). In this respect, a representative of a public administration associated with Factor 2 asserts that “The living environment must be improved for everyone” (ADM 4). In the vision of a just and sustainable city associated with Factor 2, this urban greening takes place in a high-density (S23, +1), mixed-used (S17, +2) territory guaranteeing all residents quick, easy and safe access to residential and socio-economic activities (housing, offices, shops, parcs...).

Finally, just like Factor 1, Factor 2 advocate for effective access to health equipment (S6, +4), healthy food (S5, +3), public services (S18, +3) and decent minimum income (S38, +3) to be guaranteed to all residents, especially those who are deprived of them today.

The vision of the just and sustainable city encapsulated in Factor 2 resembles in many ways elements of the well-established concept of the ‘Smart City’. While one of the first mentions of the concept was in 1998 by Van Bastelaer, it has been evolving over the past decades. Vanolo (2014) understood the Smart City to be a composition of the ideals of a green city on the one hand, and technologic futurism on the other. While we can indeed distinguish the pursuit of these two ideals in Factor 2, we can sense that there is a certain focus on technological solutions. In line with the understanding of the Smart City by de Jong et al. (2015) it can be noted that the attention lays rather on the development of infrastructure and information use rather than on targeting key environmental issues directly. The Smart City concept further highlights an economic perspective which corresponds to the vision that Factor 2 embodies. In this regard, Caraglio, Del Bo, and Nijkamp (2011) count the element of business-driven urban development as a characteristic of the Smart City concept while Neirotti et al. (2014) stress an intelligent urban development which is aiming at sustainable economic growth.

b) Q-Sorts Significantly Correlated with Factor 2

The Q-Sorts of four respondents are significantly correlated with Factor 2 (Table 12). This is thus the factor with the fewest significantly correlated Q-sorts.

Table 12. Number of Q sorts significantly correlated with Factor 2 per category of stakeholder

Category of stakeholder	Number of Q sorts significantly correlated with Factor 2
Administration and other public organisations	2

NGO or association	0
Business Federation	2
Trade union	0
Citizen movement	0
Other	0
TOTAL	4

From the 12 survey respondents who work in the administration and other public organisations, two are associated with Factor 2. These two participants are involved in the areas of biodiversity, and environmental and energy management.

From the total of four participants in our study who work for business federations, two are associated with Factor 2. They work in defending the interests of companies, and the production and supply of gas and electricity.

Appendix 4 illustrates these numbers with their respective Q-Sorts and puts them in perspective with their respective weight in the construction of Factor 2.

c) Composite Q-Sort of Factor 2

The figure below shows the composite Q-Sort of Factor 2, i.e., the average ranking of the statements in the Q-Sorts significantly correlated with Factor 2 (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Composite Q-sort for Factor 2

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
** ◀ 35. Brussels is becoming a territory where time devoted to work is severely limited.	** ◀ 20. Brussels is becoming a territory that gives priority to the interests of small, locally rooted businesses rather than those of large corporations.	1. Brussels is becoming a territory where differences, diversity and multiculturalism are recognized and taken into account in urban planning processes.	22. Brussels is becoming a territory where decent, quality work in the green economy is effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	27. Brussels is becoming a resilient territory where all residents are protected from environmental risks (floods, heat waves, pollution, etc.), particularly the most vulnerable (residents of dense areas, elderly people, etc.).	** ▶ 13. Brussels continues to evolve within the framework of a capitalist system.	10. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to energy-efficient housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	18. Brussels is becoming a territory where the offer of public services is significant and effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of them today.	** ▶ 36. Brussels is becoming a territory where digital technology plays an important role in the deployment of ecological production and consumption methods.
15. Brussels is becoming a territory where power within political institutions is in the hands of historically dominated and marginalized populations.	19. Brussels is becoming a territory where all activities collectively considered unsustainable have disappeared.	** ◀ 4. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to decent and affordable housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	34. Brussels is becoming a territory that guarantees an adequate level of training for workers to meet labor needs in the green economy.	** ◀ 12. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to soft mobility infrastructure and services is guaranteed to all residents (e.g. public transport, cycling), in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	** ▶ 23. Brussels is becoming a high-density territory which allows quick, easy and safe access to amenities and services.	** ▶ 17. Brussels is becoming, in its entirety, a mixed-use territory guaranteeing all residents easy access to all residential and socio-economic activities (housing, offices, shops, parks, etc.).	5. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to healthy food is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	6. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to health equipment is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.
** ◀ 39. Brussels becomes a territory where an income and assets ceiling is established.	11. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to an ecological individual vehicle is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of one today.	14. Brussels is becoming a territory where groups of residents act collectively in large-scale movements to radically transform urban spaces.	** ▶ 21. Brussels is becoming a territory which retains areas with low social and cultural diversity and which prevents all forms of discrimination.	30. Bruxelles is becoming a territory where effective participation in food production and distribution systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today (collective garden, cooperative, food belt, etc.).	29. Brussels is becoming a territory that reduces the use of resources and the production of waste through social innovation (resource centers, food centers, Repair Café...)	* ▶ 32. Brussels is becoming a competitive territory through the development of its leadership in the green economy.	38. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to a decent minimum income is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	** ▶ 25. Brussels is becoming a territory that reduces resource use and waste production through technological innovation.
** ◀ 24. Brussels is becoming a territory that limits the consumption of goods and services collectively considered non-essential (luxury, waste, etc.).	41. Brussels is becoming a territory whose political decisions and economic activities contribute to reducing north/south inequalities.	3. Brussels is becoming a territory where access to all forms of mobility is affordable and fairly distributed among all groups of residents.	* ◀ 9. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to renewable energy production systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	31. Brussels is becoming a territory where all food is produced locally (Belgium and neighboring regions).	37. Brussels becomes a territory where all forms of domination and marginalization have been annihilated (sexism, classism, colonialism, speciesism, etc.).	42. Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm future generations.	28. Brussels is becoming a territory that preserves and deploys vegetation networks and urban green infrastructure, in order to guarantee all forms of nature and their benefits for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.	
	26. Brussels is becoming a city that is developing a sufficient and quality social housing supply, in particular by repurposing part of its green spaces.			33. Brussels is becoming a territory providing many green jobs.	** ▶ 40. Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm neighboring regions.	2. Brussels is becoming a territory where green spaces and infrastructure are equitably distributed across the urban territory.		
			16. Brussels is becoming a territory where decision-making is organized through citizen assemblies and other horizontal processes instead of current political institutions.	8. Brussels is becoming a territory where all social groups affected by urban policies participate in an informed and effective manner in decision-making processes.	** ▶ 7. Brussels is becoming a territory where access to digital goods and services is guaranteed for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.			

Legend

- * Distinguishing statement at $P < 0.05$
- ** Distinguishing statement at $P < 0.01$
- ▶ Z-score for the statement is higher than in all other factors
- ◀ Z-score for the statement is lower than in all other factors
- Consensus Statements

d) Distinguishing Statements of Factor 2

The following table displays the distinguishing statements of Factor 2 (Table 13).

Table 13. Distinguishing statements of Factor 2

Statement Number	Factor 1		Factor 2		Factor 3	
	Q-SV	Z-Score	Q-SV	Z-Score	Q-SV	Z-Score
36	-4	-1.66	4	1.28	-3	-1.307
25	-3	-1.39	4	1.2	1	0.39
17	1	0.23	2	0.97	-2	-0.583
32	-3	-1.39	2	0.84	0	0.194
13	-4	-2.49	1	0.75	-4	-2.409
23	-2	-0.76	1	0.74	-4	-1.63
40	-2	-0.59	1	0.48	-2	-0.998
7	-2	-0.56	1	0.43	-2	-0.821
12	3	1.29	0	0.24	2	1.07
21	-3	-1.39	-1	-0.23	-3	-1.222
9	1	0.4	-1	-0.3	2	0.969
4	4	1.55	-2	-0.54	2	0.921
20	-1	-0.1	-3	-1.18	3	1.292
24	-2	-0.5	-3	-1.84	4	1.578
35	-1	-0.24	-4	-1.99	-1	-0.456
39	0	0.17	-4	-2.25	-2	-1.025

We can see in Appendix 7 that all the statements of Factor 2 above have a significant distance not only to the statement of one factor, but also to the other factor, when summed up. This shows that the ranking of statements of Factor 2 is significantly different from those of Factor 1 and 3, suggesting that the vision expressed in Factor 2 differs strongly from that of the other two factors.

The distinguishing statements of Factor 2 mirror the techno-economic perspective that strongly differentiates this factor from the other two.

Particularly the focus on technological innovation and access for all Brussels residents to digital goods and services is unique with the following statements yielding a positive score in Factor 2, while they tend to obtain negative scores for Factor 1 and 3:

Statement 36: Brussels becomes a territory where digital technology plays an important role in the deployment of ecological modes of production and consumption. (+4)

Statement 25: Brussels becomes a territory that reduces resource use and waste production through technological innovation. (+4)

Statement 7: Brussels becomes a territory where access to digital goods and services is guaranteed for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today. (+1)

Moreover, the emphasis on reinforcing the economic competitiveness of the BCR through the deployment of green economy is set through the positive score attributed to the distinguishing statement hereunder, which obtain a negative or neutral score for other factors:

Statement 32: Brussels becomes a competitive territory through the development of its leadership in the green economy. (+2)

In the same way, the statement advocating for the maintenance of the capitalist system is rated slightly desirable in Factor 2, while it received the lowest score in both other factors:

Statement 13: Brussels continues to evolve within the framework of a capitalist system. (+1)

Factor 2 also distinguishes itself from other factors by giving a higher score to the statements in favour of planning for a high-density, mixed-used city guaranteeing all Brussels' inhabitants access to every residential and socio-economic activities:

Statement 17: Brussels becomes, in its entirety, a mixed-use territory guaranteeing all residents easy access to all residential and socio-economic activities (housing, offices, shops, parks, etc.). (+2)

Statement 23: Brussels becomes a high-density territory which allows quick, easy and safe access to amenities and services. (+1)

Interestingly, compared with other factors, Factor 2 prioritise more the fact that Brussels does not harm neighbouring regions:

Statement 23: Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm neighboring regions. (+1)

In the same way, this is the factor which gives the least negative score to the statement suggesting the conservation of areas with low social and cultural diversity:

Statement 4: Brussels becomes a territory which retains areas with low social and cultural diversity and which prevents all forms of discrimination. (-2)

Conversely, Factor 2 assigns a lower score than the others to statements promoting effective access for all Brussels residents to soft mobility infrastructure and services, renewable energy production systems and decent and affordable housing:

Statement 12: Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to soft mobility infrastructure and services is guaranteed to all residents (e.g. public transport, cycling), in particular to those who are deprived of it today. (0)

Statement 9: Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to renewable energy production systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today. (-1)

Statement 4: Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to decent and affordable housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today. (-2)

Finally, economic regulation is to be limited for this factor as the very negative scoring of the following distinguishing statements illustrate:

Statement 39: Brussels becomes a territory where an income and assets ceiling is established. (-4)

Statement 35: Brussels becomes a territory where time devoted to work is severely limited. (-4)

Statement 24: Brussels becomes a territory that limits the consumption of goods and services collectively considered non-essential (luxury, waste, etc.). (-3)

Statement 20: Brussels becomes a territory that gives priority to the interests of small, locally rooted businesses rather than those of large corporations. (-3)

3.2.3. Factor 3: The 'Exnovation City'

a) Vision of Just and Sustainable City associated with Factor 3

In the vision of the 'Exnovation City', Brussels becomes a territory where all activities collectively considered unsustainable have disappeared (S19, +4). This includes notably the consumption of non-local food, all the food consumed in Brussels being produced in Belgium and neighbouring regions (S31, +3). The Brussels region also promotes the local production of renewable energy by guaranteeing effective access to all residents of Brussels to renewable energy production systems (S9, +2). It also gives priority to the interests of small locally rooted businesses rather than those of large corporations (S20, +3). In this regard, a member of NGO associated with Factor 3 states that "we must favour small structures where the sustainability of the activity and the well-being of employees are put forward"

(NGO 3). In addition to relocating the production of goods and services, this vision advocates a reduction in consumption volumes, notably by limiting the consumption of goods and services collectively considered non-essential (ex.: luxury, waste) (S24, +4). This ideal of sufficiency is reflected in the responses of a participant: "We NEED more equality AND less consumption (the AND has its full meaning here). We must cut back on the benefits of the wealthy and agree to live more 'poorly' for the 30 to 40% of the top income and wealth. We NEED "less than" policies and stop with "more than" for more people" (OTH 1). In Factor 3, effective access to soft mobility, healthy food and health equipment is further guaranteed for all Brussels residents, in particular those who are deprived today.

Moreover, as for the 'Smart City', Brussels becomes a territory that preserves and deploys vegetation networks and urban green infrastructure, in order to guarantee all forms of nature and their benefits for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today (S28, +4). These green spaces are also evenly distributed across the territory of the region (S2, +2). The urban development in the 'Exnovation City', however, differs from that of the 'Smart City' in that Brussels is not becoming a high density (S23, -4), mixed-used (S17, -2) territory, and can even be de-densified. In this respect, a participant associated with Factor 3 maintains that "Food autonomy in dense cities is IMPOSSIBLE to obtain" and asserts on this basis that "the city MUST be de-densified" (OTH 1).

The strong conception of sustainability associated with Factor 3 is reflected in the response to the post-sorting questions of a member of administration, who advocates for a city with nature: "My ideal city would be Brussels with trees and public green spaces everywhere and for everyone (...) Public roads distributed equitably among all users (...). May this rediscovered public space, freed from motorised vehicles, be reconverted into spaces for living, meeting, greenery, tree-lined streets, biodiversity (...). We must reintroduce nature into the city so that it contributes to the well-being of the inhabitants, the fauna and the flora on which humans and other living beings depend." (ADM 12). Considering that "the ecological transition is not sufficiently underway at the moment", another representative of an administration argues that "it is essential that a framework is applied at the regional scale so that political decisions and economic activities no longer exceed the limits essential to the preservation of the planet" (ADM 11).

Similarly to the 'Foundational City', the 'Exnovation City' does not promote the deployment of digital technologies (S36, -3; S7, -2), It is however not as techno-pessimistic than this one in the sense that it is rather favourable to Brussels reducing its resource use and waste production through technological innovation (S25, +1).

Ultimately, also like the to the 'Foundational City' vision, that of the 'Exnovation City' entails that the transition to a just and sustainable city requires an exit from the capitalist system (S13 -4). Many respondents associated with Factors 3 expressed themselves in that sense: "the change in economic paradigm seems essential to me. We cannot remain in a capitalist system as is currently the case." (ADM 11); "a capitalist world will not allow us to maintain our planet and human life in a decent manner. We must change the system." (NGO 5); or "The just transition begins with greater equality, respect for planetary limits and the raising of the social floor. This will not be achieved by capitalism, even green capitalism, digital technologies or equal access to harmful elements." (OTH 1).

We have chosen Factor 3 to be named 'Exnovation City' because it distinguishes itself from other factors by giving priority to statements associated with the concept 'exnovation', i.e., the deliberate exit from unsustainable industries, technologies, business models and practices. This concept emerged in Sustainable Transitions Studies in response to the 'innovation bias', which prevents us from thinking beyond development and diffusion of sustainable innovations in the governance of sustainability transitions. It invites us to think of sustainability transitions as transformation processes involving the articulation of innovation and exnovation, both deemed necessary for transforming socio-technical systems towards sustainability: On the one hand, "the maturing of alternatives determines the credibility and timing of policies targeting the exit from unsustainable industries" (Callorda Fossati et al. 2022, p. 7, personal translation). On the other hand, the exit of unsustainable socio-technical

configurations enables us to make room for the deployment of sustainable alternatives (ibidem). Innovation and exnovation can thus be seen as the ‘yin’ and ‘yang’ of sustainability transitions: they act in opposite but complementary ways and are both essential to ensure such transformation processes.

Interestingly, besides a high score for statements suggesting exnovation, many respondents associated with Factor 3 proposed exnovation policies to the post-sorting question on policies to be implemented to ensure the transition towards a just and sustainable Brussels-Capital Region. One of them even advocates explicitly for “Exnovation policy to truly initiate the ecological transition: Massive and drastic energy renovation of buildings; Proactive exit from unsustainable economic activities and proactive support for sustainable products, activities and actors; Proactive policies to end the reign of the car (...); Proactive transition towards truly sustainable food systems (...)" (ADM 11).

b) Q-Sorts Significantly Correlated with Factor 3

The Q-Sorts of ten participants are significantly correlated with Factor 3 (Table 14).

Table 14. Number of Q sorts significantly correlated with Factor 3 per category of stakeholder

Category of stakeholder	Number of Q sorts significantly correlated with Factor 3
Administration and other public organisations	4
NGO or association	5
Business Federation	0
Trade union	0
Citizen movement	0
Other	1
TOTAL	10

From all 12 study participants who work for administration and other public organisations, four are associated with Factor 3. These work in the areas raising awareness of different themes linked to the ecological transition (in particular sustainable food); financial support for projects, studies, conferences, etc. relating to the climate and social justice more generally; energy transition, climate air energy plan; urbanism.

Among the 10 respondents part of non-governmental organisations or associations, five are associated with Factor 3. They are involved in the areas of the fight against social inequality; reintegration into employment through entrepreneurial projects; regenerative economy, sustainable society, entrepreneurship; climate, environment, biodiversity; construction and logistics.

From the two respondents who indicated “other”, one is associated with Factor 3. This person describes its organisation as being both a company, a company federation and a citizen movement, that is active in the areas of circular economy, climate change mitigation, adaptation to climate change, Fighting poverty, Sufficiency policies.

Appendix 5 illustrates these respondents with their Q-Sorts and its respective weight in the construction of Factor 3.

c) Composite Q-Sort of Factor 3

The figure below depicts the average ranking of the statements in the Q-Sorts linked to Factor 3 (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Composite Q-sort for Factor 3

-4	-3	-2	-1	0	1	2	3	4
11. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to an ecological individual vehicle is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of one today.	26. Brussels is becoming a city that is developing a sufficient and quality social housing supply, in particular by repurposing part of its green spaces.	** ◀ 17. Brussels is becoming, in its entirety, a mixed-use territory guaranteeing all residents easy access to all residential and socio-economic activities (housing, offices, shops, parks, etc.).	30. Buxelles is becoming a territory where effective participation in food production and distribution systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today (collective garden, cooperative, food belt, etc.).	* 32. Brussels is becoming a competitive territory through the development of its leadership in the green economy.	29. Brussels is becoming a territory that reduces the use of resources and the production of waste through social innovation (resource centers, food centers, Repair Café...)	12. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to soft mobility infrastructure and services is guaranteed to all residents (e.g. public transport, cycling), in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	** ▶ 31. Brussels is becoming a territory where all food is produced locally (Belgium and neighboring regions).	** ▶ 19. Brussels is becoming a territory where all activities collectively considered unsustainable have disappeared.
** ◀ 23. Brussels is becoming a high-density territory which allows quick, easy and safe access to amenities and services.	21. Brussels is becoming a territory which retains areas with low social and cultural diversity and which prevents all forms of discrimination.	33. Brussels is becoming a territory providing many green jobs.	8. Brussels is becoming a territory where all social groups affected by urban policies participate in an informed and effective manner in decision-making processes.	41. Brussels is becoming a territory whose political decisions and economic activities contribute to reducing north/south inequalities.	37. Brussels becomes a territory where all forms of domination and marginalization have been annihilated (sexism, classism, colonialism, speciesism, etc.).	** ▶ 9. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to renewable energy production systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	** ▶ 20. Brussels is becoming a territory that gives priority to the interests of small, locally rooted businesses rather than those of large corporations.	** ▶ 24. Brussels is becoming a territory that limits the consumption of goods and services collectively considered non-essential (luxury, waste, etc.).
13. Brussels continues to evolve within the framework of a capitalist system.	36. Brussels is becoming a territory where digital technology plays an important role in the deployment of ecological production and consumption methods.	7. Brussels is becoming a territory where access to digital goods and services is guaranteed for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.	16. Brussels is becoming a territory where decision-making is organized through citizen assemblies and other horizontal processes instead of current political institutions.	** ◀ 10. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to energy-efficient housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	42. Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm future generations.	** 4. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to decent and affordable housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	5. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to healthy food is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	28. Brussels is becoming a territory that preserves and deploys vegetation networks and urban green infrastructure, in order to guarantee all forms of nature and their benefits for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.
	15. Brussels is becoming a territory where power within political institutions is in the hands of historically dominated and marginalized populations.	* ◀ 40. Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm neighboring regions.	34. Brussels is becoming a territory that guarantees an adequate level of training for workers to meet labor needs in the green economy.	** ◀ 38. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to a decent minimum income is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	** 25. Brussels is becoming a territory that reduces resource use and waste production through technological innovation.	22. Brussels is becoming a territory where decent, quality work in the green economy is effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	6. Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to health equipment is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	
		** 39. Brussels becomes a territory where an income and assets ceiling is established.	35. Brussels is becoming a territory where time devoted to work is severely limited.	1. Brussels is becoming a territory where differences, diversity and multiculturalism are recognized and taken into account in urban planning processes.	* ▶ 3. Brussels is becoming a territory where access to all forms of mobility is affordable and fairly distributed among all groups of residents.	2. Brussels is becoming a territory where green spaces and infrastructure are equitably distributed across the urban territory.		
			14. Brussels is becoming a territory where groups of residents act collectively in large-scale movements to radically transform urban spaces.	** ◀ 18. Brussels is becoming a territory where the offer of public services is significant and effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of them today.	27. Brussels is becoming a resilient territory where all residents are protected from environmental risks (floods, heat waves, pollution, etc.), particularly the most vulnerable (residents of dense areas, elderly people, etc.).			

Legend

- * Distinguishing statement at P< 0.05
- ** Distinguishing statement at P< 0.01
- ▶ Z-score for the statement is higher than in all other factors
- ◀ Z-score for the statement is lower than in all other factors
- Consensus Statements

d) Distinguishing Statements of Factor 3

The following table shows the distinguishing statements of Factor 3 (Table 15).

Table 15. Distinguishing statements of Factor 3

Statement Number	Factor 1		Factor 2		Factor 3	
	Q-SV	Z-Score	Q-SV	Z-Score	Q-SV	Z-Score
19	-3	-1.03	-3	-1.44	4	1.66
24	-2	-0.5	-3	-1.84	4	1.58
31	0	-0.03	0	0.15	3	1.33
20	-1	-0.1	-3	-1.18	3	1.29
9	1	0.4	-1	-0.3	2	0.97
4	4	1.55	-2	-0.54	2	0.92
25	-3	-1.39	4	1.2	1	0.39
3	-1	-0.28	-1	-0.29	1	0.37
32	-3	-1.39	2	0.84	0	0.19
10	3	1.22	2	0.98	0	0.06
38	3	1.22	3	1.06	0	0.01
18	4	1.43	3	1.08	0	-0.19
17	1	0.23	2	0.97	-2	-0.58
40	-2	-0.59	1	0.48	-2	-1
39	0	0.17	-4	-2.25	-2	-1.02
23	-2	-0.76	1	0.74	-4	-1.63

The distinguishing statements with higher scores of Factor 1 reflect the strong conception of sustainability that characterises this factor.

Factor 3 differentiates itself from the others by giving a high score to the statements promoting the exnovation of unsustainable modes of production and consumptions in the BCR, while the other factors assign negative or neutral scores to these statements:

Statement 19: Brussels becomes a territory where all activities collectively considered unsustainable have disappeared. (+4)

Statement 24: Brussels becomes a territory that limits the consumption of goods and services collectively considered non-essential (luxury, waste, etc.). (+4)

Statement 20: Brussels becomes a territory that gives priority to the interests of small, locally rooted businesses rather than those of large corporations. (+3)

Statement 31: Brussels becomes a territory where all food is produced locally (Belgium and neighbouring regions). (+3)

While statement 19 explicitly describes the results of an exnovation process – i.e., a territory where all activities collectively considered unsustainable have disappeared –, the statements 24 and 20 evoke two types of exnovation policies¹¹, one aimed at regulating unsustainable consumption patterns and another one aimed at reducing support for incumbent environmentally-damaging companies. For its part, statement 31 implicitly suggests that consumption of non-local food has been exnovated.

Factor 3 is also the one that gives higher scores to the statements promoting effective access to renewable energy production devices and all forms of mobility to all Brussels citizens, which mirrors the prioritisation of environmental sustainability objectives characterising this factor.

Statement 9: Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to renewable energy production systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today. (+2)

Statement 3: Brussels becomes a territory where access to all forms of mobility is affordable and fairly distributed among all groups of residents. (+1)

Conversely, Factor 3 is the factor that assigned the lowest score for the following statements:

¹¹ For a typology of exnovation policies, see Kivima et Kern (2016).

Statements 10: Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to energy-efficient housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today. (0)

Statements 38: Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to a decent minimum income is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today. (0)

Statements 38: Brussels becomes a territory where the offer of public services is significant and effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of them today. (0)

Statement 40: Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm neighbouring regions. (-2)

Statements 17: Brussels becomes, in its entirety, a mixed-use territory guaranteeing all residents easy access to all residential and socio-economic activities (housing, offices, shops, parks, etc.). (-2)

These lower scores are difficult to interpret, as the answers to the post-sorting questionnaire do not provide any explanatory elements.

Finally, Factor 3 is distinguished from the other factors by attributing an extreme negative score to the statement promoting the evolution of Brussels into a dense territory:

Statement 23: Brussels becomes a high-density territory which allows quick, easy and safe access to amenities and services. (-4)

3.3. Similarities and Differences Between Factors

This section provides an overview of the main similarities and differences between the three factors outlined in the previous section. The similarities between the factors are deduced from the statements that have a similar average score for all three factors, while the differences are derived from the statements that obtain significantly different average scores from one factor to another. This overview of the similarities and differences between the factors thus enables us to highlight the 'areas of consensus' and the 'area of disagreement' or 'terms of the debate' among Brussels' stakeholders on what a just and sustainable city should look like.

The following table ascendingly ranks the different statements based on their Z-Score Variance, a value reflecting the level of difference between the average score of each of the three factors (Table 16). The higher the Z-Score variance, the higher the difference between the average score of each factor, and vice versa. This table thus provides a ranking of the statements into a 'consensus versus disagreement' scale, with the most consensual statements at the top of the table, and the least consensual ones at the bottom.

Table 16. Ranking of statements according to their Z-Score variance¹². Positive average scores are shown in green, negative ones in red. The more intense the colour, the higher the score.

REF	Statement	Factor 1	Factor 2	Factor 3	Z-Score Variance	
		Q-SV	Q-SV	Q-SV		
6	Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to health equipment is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	2	4	3	0.001	Consensus
29	Brussels is becoming a territory that reduces the use of resources and the production of waste through social innovation (resource centers, food centers, Repair Café...)	1	1	1	0.005	↑
16	Brussels is becoming a territory where decision-making is organized through citizen assemblies and other horizontal processes instead of current political institutions.	-1	-1	-1	0.007	
5	Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to healthy food is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	3	3	3	0.013	
8	Brussels is becoming a territory where all social groups affected by urban policies participate in an informed and effective manner in decision-making processes.	1	0	-1	0.059	
11	Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to an ecological individual vehicle is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of one today.	-4	-3	-4	0.074	
37	Brussels becomes a territory where all forms of domination and marginalization have been annihilated (sexism, classism, colonialism, speciesism, etc.).	2	1	1	0.076	
1	Brussels is becoming a territory where differences, diversity and multiculturalism are recognized and taken into account in urban planning processes.	0	-2	0	0.100	
22	Brussels is becoming a territory where decent, quality work in the green economy is effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	1	-1	2	0.132	
41	Brussels is becoming a territory whose political decisions and economic activities contribute to reducing north/south inequalities.	-1	-2	0	0.137	
3	Brussels is becoming a territory where access to all forms of mobility is affordable and fairly distributed among all groups of residents.	-1	-1	1	0.141	
33	Brussels is becoming a territory providing many green jobs.	-1	0	-2	0.141	
30	Buxelles is becoming a territory where effective participation in food production and distribution systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today (collective garden, cooperative, food belt, etc.).	1	0	-1	0.142	
14	Brussels is becoming a territory where groups of residents act collectively in large-scale movements to radically transform urban spaces.	0	-2	-1	0.144	
27	Brussels is becoming a resilient territory where all residents are protected from environmental risks (floods, heat waves, pollution, etc.), particularly the most vulnerable (residents of dense areas, elderly people, etc.).	2	0	1	0.173	
28	Brussels is becoming a territory that preserves and deploys vegetation networks and urban green infrastructure, in order to guarantee all forms of nature and their benefits for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.	2	-3	-4	0.229	
2	Brussels is becoming a territory where green spaces and infrastructure are equitably distributed across the urban territory.	0	2	2	0.236	
34	Brussels is becoming a territory that guarantees an adequate level of training for workers to meet labor needs in the green economy.	2	-1	-1	0.262	
15	Brussels is becoming a territory where power within political institutions is in the hands of historically dominated and marginalized populations.	-2	-4	-3	0.270	
42	Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm future generations.	-4	2	1	0.287	
12	Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to soft mobility infrastructure and services is guaranteed to all residents (e.g. public transport, cycling), in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	3	0	2	0.305	
10	Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to energy-efficient housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	3	2	0	0.377	
21	Brussels is becoming a territory which retains areas with low social and cultural diversity and which prevents all forms of discrimination.	-3	-1	-3	0.392	
9	Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to renewable energy production systems is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	1	-1	2	0.404	
38	Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to a decent minimum income is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	3	3	0	0.431	
7	Brussels is becoming a territory where access to digital goods and services is guaranteed for all residents, in particular those who are deprived of them today.	-2	1	-2	0.438	
26	Brussels is becoming a city that is developing a sufficient and quality social housing supply, in particular by repurposing part of its green spaces.	0	-2	-3	0.520	
31	Brussels is becoming a territory where all food is produced locally (Belgium and neighboring regions).	0	0	3	0.545	
40	Brussels becomes a territory whose political decisions and economic activities do not harm future generations.	-2	1	-2	0.586	
17	Brussels is becoming, in its entirety, a mixed-use territory guaranteeing all residents easy access to all residential and socio-economic activities (housing, offices, shops, parks, etc.).	1	2	-2	0.601	
18	Brussels is becoming a territory where the offer of public services is significant and effectively accessible to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of them today.	-4	3	0	0.723	
35	Brussels is becoming a territory where time devoted to work is severely limited.	-1	-4	-1	0.906	
4	Brussels is becoming a territory where effective access to decent and affordable housing is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today.	4	-2	2	1.151	
32	Brussels is becoming a competitive territory through the development of its leadership in the green economy.	-3	2	0	1.324	
23	Brussels is becoming a high-density territory which allows quick, easy and safe access to amenities and services.	-2	1	-4	1.434	
39	Brussels becomes a territory where an income and assets ceiling is established.	0	-4	-2	1.457	
20	Brussels is becoming a territory that gives priority to the interests of small, locally rooted businesses rather than those of large corporations.	-1	-3	3	1.532	
25	Brussels is becoming a territory that reduces resource use and waste production through technological innovation.	-3	4	1	1.753	
36	Brussels is becoming a territory where digital technology plays an important role in the deployment of ecological production and consumption methods.	-4	4	-3	2.587	
19	Brussels is becoming a territory where all activities collectively considered unsustainable have disappeared.	-3	-3	4	2.820	
24	Brussels is becoming a territory that limits the consumption of goods and services collectively considered non-essential (luxury, waste, etc.).	-2	-3	4	2.969	↓
13	Brussels continues to evolve within the framework of a capitalist system.	-4	1	-4	3.415	Disagreement

On the basis of this table, the rest of the section defines the areas of consensus and the major terms of debate between factors.

¹² Note that both S3 and S33 have a rounded Z-Score variance of 0.141, yet their exact value is 0.140707 and 0.140949, respectively.

3.3.1. Similarities Between Factors: Area of Consensus

Several statements have a very similar average score for the three factors, thus corresponding to ‘areas of consensus’. Among these statements, only two obtain a high average score for each factor and can therefore be considered key components of all the three visions of a just and sustainable city for Brussels:

Statement 6: Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to health equipment is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today. (+2, +4, +3)

Statement 5: Brussels becomes a territory where effective access to healthy food is guaranteed to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today. (+3, +3, +3)

As previously explained, these statements are also part of the five statements with the highest total score (see section 3.1.1. Statements rated as the Most Desirable). Interestingly, both relate to health. This suggests that despite the major differences between them, the three visions of a just and sustainable city defined in this study all converge on the importance of the health of Brussels’ residents.

A consensus also seems to emerge on the role of social innovation in the transition to a just and sustainable city. The statement 29, advocating for Brussels to become a territory that reduces the use of resources and the production of waste through social innovation (“ressourceries”, food sharing, Repair Cafés...), obtains a similar positive average score (+1, +1, +1) for all the three factors.

Similarly, the statement 37, promoting an annihilation of all forms of domination and marginalisation (sexism, classism, colonialism, speciesism...) in Brussels, also gets a similar positive average score (+2, +1, +1) for all the three factors.

On the other end of the spectrum, the statement 11, which strives for guaranteeing effective access to an ecological individual vehicle to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today is ranked very negatively by all the factors (-4, -3, -4). It is also one of the two statements with the lowest total score identified previously (see section 3.1.1. Statements rated as the least Desirable). The reasons behind this apparent consensus on the low desirability of providing access to an ecological individual vehicle for all may however differ from one respondent to another. On the one hand, some might not want that everyone is by default entitled to the ownership of an individual vehicle for fear of the traffic congestion that an increase in the number of car users could generate. On the other hand, others could oppose it because they defend a vision of the city with fewer or no more individual vehicles. Such positions in favour of limiting car use in the city has been observed in the responses to the post-sorting questionnaire of several participants, most of which are associated with Factor 3. For instance, to the question of key policies to be implemented to ensure the transition towards a just and sustainable Brussels Region, a member of administration associated with Factor 3 call for implementing “Proactive policies to end the reign of the car (no more company cars, infrastructure to drastically limit car use in the city with relief parking on the outskirts, reviewing roads to promote soft mobility)” (ADM 11). In the same vein, a representative of an NGO also associated with Factor 3 advocates to “Ban company cars!!” (NGO 3).

3.3.2. Differences Between Factors: Terms of the Debate

The statements with the highest Z-score variance – i.e., those for which the average scores are the most different between the three factors – correspond to the main ‘terms of debate’ on what a just and sustainable city should look like.

The most prevalent point of disagreement concerns the maintenance of the economic and social regime in place. The statement 11 suggesting that Brussels continues to evolve within the framework of a capitalist system is indeed the one with the highest variance in Z-Scores. This statement generates disagreement between, on the one hand, Factors 1 and 3, who both give it an extreme negative score (-4), and, on the other hand, Factor 2, who ranked it slightly positively (+1). This contrast reflects an

important dividing line opposing 'transformative' and 'affirmative' conceptions of a just and sustainable city. According to the 'transformative' conception carried by Factors 1 and 3, capitalism is a root cause of contemporary social and ecological problems, and it is necessary to escape from it to ensure the transition towards a just and sustainable city. As for the reformist view defended by Factor 2, it is a question of mitigating the social and ecological impacts of capitalism by improving it.

Another major disagreement between the Factors lies in the place of exnovation in the transition to a just and sustainable city. The three statements promoting explicitly the purposive termination of unsustainable mode of production and consumption in Brussels have rather negative average scores in Factor 1, very negative average scores in Factor 2, and very positive average scores in Factor 3:

Statement 24: Brussels becomes a territory that limits the consumption of goods and services collectively considered non-essential (luxury, waste, etc.). (-1, -3, +3)

Statement 19: Brussels becomes a territory where all activities collectively considered unsustainable have disappeared. (-3, -3, +4)

Statement 20: Brussels becomes a territory that gives priority to the interests of small, locally rooted businesses rather than those of large corporations. (-1, -3, +3)

While Factor 3 promotes exnovation to accelerate and reinforce the ecological transition, Factor 2 opposes public intervention to regulate the economy. Factor 1's position on exnovation cannot be explained based on the answers to the post-sorting questions. It is therefore difficult to define whether the low score assigned to statements promoting exnovation is linked to opposition to exnovation or a deprioritization in favour of other dimensions, such as the fulfilment of fundamental needs.

Another major point of debate between the factors is the role of technology, and notably digital technology, in the deployment of ecological modes of production and consumption. The two statements suggesting an important role of technological progress in ecological transition obtain very negative average scores in Factor 1, very positive average scores in Factor 2, and mixed average scores in Factor 3:

Statement 36: Brussels becomes a territory where digital technology plays an important role in the deployment of ecological modes of production and consumption. (-4, +4, -3)

Statement 25: Brussels becomes a territory that reduces resource use and waste production through technological innovation. (-3, +4, +1)

The question of the place of technology is thus one of the main differences between the low-tech vision of Factor 1 and the techno-optimistic vision of Factor 2. Factor 3's position on the issue is less clear-cut in the sense that it is generally favourable to using technological innovation for reducing resource use and waste production, but unfavourable to putting digital at the service of the ecological transition. This could be explained by the environmental impacts associated with the deployment of digital technology.

The establishment of a ceiling on income and assets in Brussels also generates disagreements between the Factors, with the statement 28 promoting this policy obtaining a neutral average score (0) in Factor 1, a very negative average score (-4) in Factor 2 and a negative average score (-2) in Factor 3. Factor 1's neutral score for this statement masks differences within the factor, with three of the fifteen respondents associated with it assigning an extreme positive score to it, one of them asserting that it is a temporary solution to fight against social and ecological problems. The very clear opposition to the establishment of an income and assets ceiling in Factor 2 can be explained by its rejection of any form of public intervention in the economy mentioned previously. The relatively negative score for Factor 3 cannot be interpreted on the basis of the answers to the questions.

The question of the densification of Brussels is also a significant point of disagreement between the factors. Indeed, while Factor 2 assigns a positive average score (+1) to the statement 23 according to which Brussels becomes a high-density territory which allows quick, easy and safe access to amenities

and services, this statement receives from Factor 1 and Factor 3 respectively negative (-2) and very negative (-4) average scores. In this regard, a respondent associated with Factor 3 points out the incompatibility between high density and food autonomy, and promotes, on this basis, a de-densification of Brussels.

Another significant point of debate concerns the priority given to the region's economic competitiveness objectives. The statement 32 suggesting that Brussels becomes a competitive territory through the development of its leadership in the green economy indeed gets a very negative average score (-3) in Factor 1, a positive average score (+2) in Factor 2 and a neutral average score (0) in Factor 3. While Factor 2 promotes the sustainable economic development of the BCR, Factor 1 gives more priority to the fulfilment of human needs for all without comprising those of future generations. In this sense, we observe a clear dividing line between Factor 2 and Factor 1, with the first adhering to the green growth model and the second to the post-growth model. The position of Factor 3 on this question is less clear.

A final aspect of the debate that we believe is relevant to highlight concerns the guarantee of effective access to decent and affordable housing to all Brussels residents. Statement 4 promoting the fulfilment of universal access to decent and affordable housing obtains an extreme positive average score (+4) in Factor 1, a negative average score (-2) in Factor 2 and a positive average score (+2) in Factor 3. The extreme positive score of Factor 1 is not surprising, considering that this factor prioritises the provision of fundamental needs and that having decent and affordable housing constitutes a fundamental need which conditions the fulfilment of other needs such as having good health. The answers to the post-sorting questions do not allow us to explain the negative average score of Factor 2 for this statement.

4. Discussion, Conclusion and Perspectives

Considering the lack of integration between the visions of the ‘just city’ and those of the ‘sustainable city’ (Fransolet et al., 2023), the main objective of this research was to explore urban visions that explicitly combine social justice and environmental sustainability objectives. With that aim in mind, we carried out a survey based on a Q-methodology to explore the variety of perspectives on the just *and* sustainable city for Brussels-capital Region. The Q-survey of 32 Brussels stakeholders allowed us to define three main contrasted visions of a just and sustainable city: The ‘Smart City’, the ‘Foundational City’ and the ‘Exnovation City’. The main distinguishing characteristics of these visions of the just and sustainable city reflecting the different perspectives of Brussels' stakeholders are summarised in the figure below (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Overview of the three visions of a just and sustainable city in Brussels-Capital-Region¹³

The vision of the ‘Foundational City’ is the one with the highest number of survey respondents endorsing it, while the ‘Smart City’ vision is the one with the fewest. Concerning the type of stakeholder supporting the different visions identified, we find members of administrations and other public organisations subscribing to each of the three visions. On their part, the representatives of the NGOs and associations consulted promote either the ‘Foundational City’ or the ‘Exnovation City’ visions. As for the business’s federations, the two respondents representing eco-companies embrace the ‘Foundational City’ vision, while the other two representing incumbent companies adhere to the ‘Smart City’ vision. Finally, all the three trade unionists and the only member of a citizen's movement who took part in the survey support the vision of the ‘Foundational City’.

For each of the three visions of the just and sustainable city, a specific conception of ‘just sustainability’ can be distinguished. In the ‘Smart City’, it equates inclusive and sustainable economic development, i.e., an economic growth decoupled from its environmental degradation and delivering social justice. The ‘Foundational City’ abandons the imperatives of economic growth and understands ‘just

¹³ The pictures were generated with artificial intelligence.

sustainability' as a juxtaposition of intragenerational justice – i.e., justice between different humans of the present generation – and intergenerational justice – i.e., justice between humans of different generations –. The 'Exnovation City' goes beyond an anthropocentric conception of justice and interprets 'just sustainability' as an integration of ecological justice – i.e., justice for nature – with environmental justice – i.e., justice between different humans in relation to their natural environment –. Interestingly, the conceptions of just sustainability associated with each of the visions resonates with existing conceptual framework of just sustainability: that of the 'Smart City' with the 'Sustainable Developments Goals'¹⁴ (SDGs) framework of the United Nations, that of the 'Foundational City' with the 'Doughnut'¹⁵ of social and planetary boundaries theory elaborated by Kate Raworth, and that of the 'Exnovate City' with the 'Social-Ecological Loop' model proposed by the French economist Eloi Laurent (2023). On this basis, the three visions can also be classified in a continuum according to the extent of the transformation of the current political economy they imply, the 'Smart City' being the most affirmative vision and the 'Exnovation city' the most transformative. This classification echoes the results of a research conducted by the Just Transition Research Collaborative, which defines, based on the literature, four main ideal-typical visions of just transition differentiated according to the scale of the transformation of the political economy they entail: the status quo, managerial reform, structural reform, and transformative approaches (Morena et al., 2018). Our research complements this one by exploring the empirical manifestation of increasingly transformative visions of just transition on a city scale.

These three visions of the just and sustainable city can further be distinguished by the relative priority they give to the objectives of economic growth, social justice, and environmental sustainability. The 'Smart city' aims at concurrently delivering these three objectives of sustainable development. However, if achieving an absolute, net and sufficiently rapid decoupling between economic growth and its environmental degradation prove impossible, the 'Smart City' will tend to neglect environmental sustainability in favour of economic growth, which is seen as a source of trickle-down prosperity (Laurent, 2021). In the same way, if a conflict arises between the objectives of economic growth and social justice, the 'Smart City' will tend to put economic development first. More or less explicitly framed within a post-growth paradigm, the 'Foundational City' and the 'Exnovation City' both put the emphasis on social justice and environmental sustainability objectives. Nevertheless, if a trade-off arises between these two objectives, the 'Foundational City' will tend to prioritise the fulfilment of fundamental human needs and social equity, while the 'Exnovation City' will put the priority on the preservation and restoration of natural heritage deemed necessary for sustaining a good and fulfilling life for all. The priority differential between the three visions of the just and sustainable city reflects the difficulties of balancing economic growth, social justice and environmental sustainability. There are indeed inherent tensions and conflicts between these three objectives of sustainable development, which make their simultaneous pursuit difficult, if not impossible (Gilbert 2014). This challenge of jointly fostering GDP growth, a welfare state and an ecological transition is framed by Laurent (2021) as an "impossible trinity" or "trilemma".

Beyond this priority differential, the cross-analysis of these visions offers additional insights on the terms of the debate among Brussels' stakeholders on what a just and sustainable city should look like. The main points of disagreement concern the future of the capitalist system and the neo-liberal approach to the city, the place of exnovation in the transition to a just and sustainable city, the role of technology – and notably digital technology – in the deployment of ecological modes of production and consumption, the establishment of a ceiling on income and assets, the (de-)densification of the city, and the provision of universal access to decent and affordable housing in Brussels. Some of these points of disagreement echo the dividing lines existing between the visions of the 'just city' and the 'sustainable city' conceptualised in the academic literature. The maintenance of the capitalist regime is, for instance, one of the important dividing lines between the different visions of the 'just city', which

¹⁴ <https://sdgs.un.org/>

¹⁵ <https://www.kateraworth.com/doughnut/>

notably opposed the transformative vision of David Harvey to Suzan Fainstein's more affirmative approach. The role of technological development is, for its part, a key demarcation point between visions of the sustainable city, opposing technocentric visions – e.g. smart city, low-carbon city and circular city – to visions placing less emphasis on technology – e.g. sustainable city, green city and eco-city – (Fransolet et al., 2023). More fundamentally, the terms of the debate among Brussels' stakeholders on what a just and sustainable city should look like echoes those identified in a Q-survey of Belgian stakeholders on just transition. This study carried out by La Gioia and colleagues (2023), indeed, highlighted a clear divide between those supporting the advent of 'green neoliberalism' and 'eco-capitalism', and those promoting a transformation of the economic model. Our research complements this Q-survey of Belgian stakeholders by considering issues specific to the metropolitan context, such as (de-)densification and access to decent affordable housing.

Besides the divergences, the analysis has highlighted several areas of consensus between the visions of a just and sustainable city in Brussels. The most striking point of convergence between the three visions concerns the high priority given to the health of the people of Brussels. Indeed, each of the three visions places great importance on guaranteeing effective access to health equipment and healthy food to all residents, in particular to those who are deprived of it today. This emphasis on health could be an effect of the COVID 19 pandemic, which has put health and its inextricable link with social and environmental problems in the spotlight (Laurent, 2019). The focus on health in the three visions of a just and sustainable city echoes the 'just ecofeminist healthy city' vision conceptualised by Margarita Triguero-Mas et al. (2022). This vision of a just and sustainable city, which has been developed in response to the COVID-19 pandemic, incorporates "care, intersectional social inequalities, and environmental justice to the healthy cities approach" (p. 355). An in-depth analysis and open discussion on the 'just ecofeminist healthy city' vision could be instrumental in feeding the elaboration of a shared vision of a just and sustainable city for Brussels. More fundamentally, the consensus on the prioritisation of health among Brussels stakeholders paves the way for the adoption of 'full health' as a compass to guide the just transition in Brussels. The concept of 'full health', as proposed by Laurent (2019), does indeed seem particularly fruitful for integrating objectives of social justice and environmental sustainability.

Applying the Q-Analysis to explore what a just and sustainable city could look like has thus demonstrated to be very insightful. It enabled us to identify and explore three original visions of a city bridging social justice and environmental sustainability objectives, which reflect the contrasted perspective of Brussels' stakeholders on the desirable future for their region. Not only did it help to determine the areas in which there is disagreement between the stakeholders, but importantly, it also has also proven to be an effective tool for finding out the areas of consensus in the vision of a just and sustainable city. By contributing to understanding the contours of the future(s) towards which just urban transitions could orient, alongside the main disagreements and consensus on the issue, the Q-survey of Brussels' stakeholders provides fruitful ground for an open debate on just transitions in Brussels-Capital Region and other metropolitan areas.

This research presents, however, several limitations and would benefit from further investigation. A first limitation relates to the sample and the low representativeness of certain types of actors in it. The group of respondents indeed included many members of public institutions and NGO or associations, but few representatives of business federations, trade unions and citizens' movements. The massive rejection of the capitalist system observed in this research is symptomatic of the over-representation of critical actors compared to actors of the incumbent regime in the survey. Another limitation is linked to the online survey method which did not allow us to (fully) understand the point of view of the stakeholders on certain statements. This is particularly the case for statements relating to procedural justice and recognition that obtained rather neutral scores and were little discussed by respondents in the post-sorting questionnaire. A third major limitation is associated with the fact that we had to limit the number of statements so that the questionnaire was not too long, which means that certain dimensions of the just and sustainable city were not considered in this research. These limits thus open

the way to more in-depth qualitative research on the visions of a just and sustainable city with a wider panel of Brussels' stakeholders. In this context, the three visions of the just and sustainable city defined in the present research could be used as a basis to be discussed, enriched and complemented with alternative urban visions integrating social justice and environmental sustainability objectives.

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Appendix

Appendix 1. Original Q-set in French

REF	Statements
1	Bruxelles devient un territoire où les différences, la diversité et le multiculturalisme sont reconnus et pris en compte dans les processus de planification urbaine.
2	Bruxelles devient un territoire où les espaces et infrastructures vertes sont équitablement répartis sur le territoire urbain.
3	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès à toutes les formes de mobilité est abordable et équitablement réparti entre tous les groupes d'habitants.
4	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès effectif à un logement décent et abordable est garanti à tous les habitants.tes, en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
5	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès effectif à une alimentation saine est garantie à tous les habitants.e.s, en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
6	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès effectif aux équipements de santé est garanti à tous les habitant.e.s., en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
7	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès aux biens et services numériques est garanti pour tous.tes les habitant.e.s, en particulier à celle/ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
8	Bruxelles devient un territoire où tous les groupes sociaux concernés par les politiques urbaines participent de manière informée et effective aux processus de prise de décision.
9	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès effectif aux systèmes de productions d'énergie renouvelable est garanti à tous.tes les habitant.e.s., en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
10	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès effectif à un logement efficient sur le plan énergétique est garanti à tous.tes les habitant.e.s., en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
11	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès effectif à un véhicule individuel écologique est garanti à tous.tes les habitant.e.s., en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
12	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès effectif à des infrastructures et services de mobilité douce est garanti à tous.tes les habitant.e.s (e.g. transport en commun, vélo), en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
13	Bruxelles continue à évoluer dans le cadre d'un système capitaliste.
14	Bruxelles devient un territoire où des groupes d'habitants agissent collectivement dans des mouvements d'ampleur pour transformer radicalement les espaces urbains.
15	Bruxelles devient un territoire où le pouvoir au sein des institutions politiques est entre les mains des populations historiquement dominées et marginalisées.
16	Bruxelles devient un territoire où la prise de décision s'organise à travers des assemblées citoyennes et autres processus horizontaux en lieu et place des institutions politiques actuelles.
17	Bruxelles devient, dans son intégralité, un territoire à usage mixte garantissant à tous les habitants un accès facile à l'ensemble des activités résidentielles et socio-économiques (logements, bureaux, commerces, ...).
18	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'offre de services publics est importante et effectivement accessible à tous.tes les habitants, en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
19	Bruxelles devient un territoire où toutes les activités considérées collectivement comme non durables ont disparu.
20	Bruxelles devient un territoire qui donne la priorité aux intérêts des petites entreprises, enracinées localement, plutôt qu'à ceux des grandes sociétés.
21	Bruxelles devient un territoire qui conserve des zones à faible mixité sociale et culturelle et qui prévient toutes formes de discrimination.
22	Bruxelles devient un territoire où un travail décent et de qualité dans l'économie verte est effectivement accessible à tous.tes les habitants.tes, en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
23	Bruxelles devient un territoire à haute densité qui permet un accès rapide, facile et sûr aux commodités et aux services.

24	Bruxelles devient un territoire qui limite la consommation de biens et de services considérés collectivement comme non-essentiels (luxe, gaspillage, ...).
25	Bruxelles devient un territoire qui réduit l'utilisation de ressources et la production de déchets via l'innovation technologique.
26	Bruxelles devient une ville qui développe une offre de logement social suffisante et de qualité notamment en réaffectant une partie de ses espaces verts.
27	Bruxelles devient un territoire résilient où tous les habitant.e.s sont à l'abri des risques environnementaux (inondations, vagues de chaleur, pollution, ...), en particulier les plus vulnérables (habitants des zones denses, personnes âgées, ...).
28	Bruxelles devient un territoire qui préserve et déploie les réseaux de végétation et les infrastructures vertes urbaines, afin de garantir toutes les formes de nature et leurs avantages pour tous.les habitant.e.s, en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
29	Bruxelles devient un territoire qui réduit l'utilisation de ressources et la production de déchets via l'innovation sociale (ressourceries, donneries alimentaires, Repair Cafés, ...).
30	Bruxelles devient un territoire où la participation effective aux systèmes de production et de distribution alimentaires est garantie à tous.les habitant.e.s., en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui (jardin collectif, coopérative, ceinture alimentaire, ...).
31	Bruxelles devient un territoire où tous les aliments sont produits localement (Belgique et régions limitrophes).
32	Bruxelles devient un territoire compétitif via le développement de son leadership dans l'économie verte.
33	Bruxelles devient un territoire pourvoyeur de nombreux emplois verts.
34	Bruxelles devient un territoire qui garantit un niveau de formation adéquat des travailleur.euses pour répondre aux besoins de main d'œuvre dans l'économie verte.
35	Bruxelles devient un territoire où le temps consacré au travail est fortement limité.
36	Bruxelles devient un territoire où le numérique joue un rôle important dans le déploiement des modes de productions et de consommations écologiques.
37	Bruxelles devient un territoire où toutes formes de domination et de marginalisation ont été annihilées (sexisme, classisme, colonialisme, spécisme, ...).
38	Bruxelles devient un territoire où l'accès effectif à un revenu minimum décent est garanti à tous.les habitant.e.s, en particulier à ceux qui en sont privés aujourd'hui.
39	Bruxelles devient un territoire où un plafond de revenu et de patrimoine est établi.
40	Bruxelles devient un territoire dont les décisions politiques et les activités économiques ne portent pas préjudice aux régions limitrophes.
41	Bruxelles devient un territoire dont les décisions politiques et les activités économiques contribuent à la réduction des inégalités nord/sud.
42	Bruxelles devient un territoire dont les décisions politiques et les activités économiques ne portent pas préjudice aux générations futures.

Appendix 2. Introductory and Post-Survey Questions

Introductory Questions
1. What type of organisation are you part of?
2. If you chose "other", could you specify the type of organisation you belong to?
3. What area are you active in (e.g. climate change mitigation, poverty alleviation, circular economy, etc.)?

Post-Survey Questions
1. Could you explain your choice for the statements to which you assigned an extreme score (+4 and -4)? (Optional answer)
2. Are there important elements of your vision of a just and sustainable city that you have not found in the proposals you have ranked? If yes, which ones? (Optional answer)

3. In your opinion, what would be the key policy(ies) to be implemented to ensure the transition towards a fair and sustainable Brussels Region? (Optional answer)

Appendix 3. Weight of Q-Sorts significantly correlated to Factor 1

Factor 1	Sorts Weight	
Statement Number	Q Sort	Weight
23	ADM10	10
9	TRA2	7.24545
4	TRA3	5.8239
27	ADM3	5.78515
1	FED1	5.5754
30	ADM1	5.17796
24	NGO10	5.09761
5	ADM9	4.96216
26	TRA1	4.84034
6	NGO8	4.38838
25	NGO9	4.32251
13	OTH2	4.23868
8	CYT1	4.22395
10	NGO2	3.7088
22	FED4	3.64165

Appendix 4. Weight of Q-Sorts significantly correlated to Factor 2

Factor 2	Sorts Weight	
Statement Number	Q Sort	Weight
32	FED2	8.94176
7	ADM6	6.52793
16	FED3	4.92951
11	ADM4	4.53365

Appendix 5. Weight of Q-Sorts significantly correlated to Factor 3

Factor 3	Sorts Weight	
Statement Number	Q Sort	Weight
12	NGO4	6.57168
17	ADM12	5.49461
2	NGO1	4.83157
29	ADM8	4.58722
28	NGO6	4.28787
3	ADM11	3.77986
19	NGO5	3.05081
31	ADM7	2.55276
15	NGO3	2.22519

Appendix 6. Distinguishing Statements Factor 1

Statement Number	Factor 1-2	Factor 1-3	Factor 1-2+1-3
4	2.091	0.629	2.72
42	0.626	1.065	1.691
27	0.69	0.751	1.441
34	0.67	1.002	1.672
9	0.7	-0.569	0.131
17	-0.737	0.813	0.076
39	2.417	1.195	3.612
26	1.189	1.307	2.496
14	0.671	0.645	1.316
2	-0.891	-0.775	-1.666
20	1.077	-1.392	-0.315
24	1.341	-2.078	-0.737
40	-1.073	0.408	-0.665
23	-1.498	0.87	-0.628
15	1.034	0.461	1.495
25	-2.594	-1.78	-4.374
32	-2.232	-1.584	-3.816

Appendix 7. Distinguishing Statements Factor 2

Statement Number	Factor 2-1	Factor 2-3	Factor 2-1+2-3
36	2.94	2.587	5.527
25	2.59	0.81	3.4
17	0.74	1.553	2.293
32	2.23	0.646	2.876
13	3.24	3.159	6.399
23	1.5	2.37	3.87
40	1.07	1.478	2.548
7	0.99	1.251	2.241
12	-1.05	-0.83	-1.88
21	1.16	0.992	2.152
9	-0.7	-1.269	-1.969
4	-2.09	-1.461	-3.551
20	-1.08	-2.472	-3.552
24	-1.34	-3.418	-4.758
35	-1.75	-1.534	-3.284
39	-2.42	-1.225	-3.645

Appendix 8. Distinguishing Statements Factor 3

Statement Number	Factor 3-1	Factor 3-2	Factor 3-1+3-2
19	2.69	3.1	5.79
24	2.08	3.42	5.5
31	1.36	1.18	2.54
20	1.39	2.47	3.86
9	0.57	1.27	1.84
4	-0.63	1.46	0.83
25	1.78	-0.81	0.97
3	0.65	0.66	1.31
32	1.58	-0.65	0.93
10	-1.16	-0.92	-2.08
38	-1.21	-1.05	-2.26
18	-1.62	-1.27	-2.89
17	-0.81	-1.55	-2.36
40	-0.41	-1.48	-1.89
39	-1.19	1.23	0.04
23	-0.87	-2.37	-3.24